

Open Autonomous programmable cloud appS & smart EdgE Sensors

OASEES D6.2 Business Plan

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AI: Artificial Intelligence

D&C: Dissemination and Communications

DCM: Dissemination and Communication Manager

EAB: External Advisory Board

KPIs: Key Performance Indicators

PC: Project Coordinator

TM: Technical Manager

WP: Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

OASEES is a European project funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101092702. Its goal is to create an open, decentralized, intelligent, programmable edge framework for Swarm architectures and applications, leveraging the Decentralized Autonomous Organization (DAO) paradigm and integrating Human-in-the-Loop (HITL) processes for efficient decision-making. The OASEES vision is to provide open tools and secure environments for swarm programming and orchestration for numerous fields, in a completely decentralized manner. An important aspect of this process is identification and identity management, in which OASEES targets the implementation of a portable and privacy-preserving ID federation system, for edge devices and services, with full compliance and compatibility to GAIA-X federation and IDSA trust directives and specifications. This situation solidifies the need for an integrated enabler framework tailored to the edge’s extreme data processing demands, using different edge accelerators, i.e. GPU, NPU, SNN, and Quantum.

OASEES’ primary objectives are:

Build rapid development kits (RDKs) for an open programmable framework across different smart edge nodes, while incorporating efficient cloud-to-edge continuum intelligence across heterogeneous target environments.

Build a secure, trustworthy, and decentralized edge ecosystem with native device support by integrating Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) for a portable digital identity that does not depend on any centralized authority. The OASEES decentralized device identity will be a new class of identifier that fulfills all four requirements: persistence, global resolvability, cryptographic verifiability, and decentralization.

Design a decentralized, agile and secure architecture for collaborative smart nodes at the edge, supporting heterogeneous device communication, backed by the Decentralized Autonomous Organization (DAO) paradigm integration.

Demonstrate the framework and programmability toolkit in a set of different vertical use cases and evaluate the benefits across different sectors.

Maximize the impact of the OASEES results via extensive communication, scientific dissemination, and exploitation activities. Foster the creation of an open-source community around the OASEES solution, engaging a diverse set of stakeholders.

OASEES gathers a strong and complementary consortium of 21 different partners from 9 different European countries (Greece, Italy, Spain, France, Netherlands, Germany, Belgium, Romania, and Luxemburg). The consortium gathers a wide range of companies, including SMEs, Academia, Research Institutes, and NGOs. OASEES will run from January 1st, 2023 to December 31st, 2025. A full list of the partners and their funding can be found at: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101092702>.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

This deliverable D6.2 “Business Plan” is the first version of the exploitation strategy devised for the OASEES project and includes the outputs of Task 6.2: Socio-Economical Sustainability Analysis and OASEES Ecosystem Business Models and Uptake Roadmap. Specifically, it encompasses the initial design of the exploitation strategy, closely collaborating with partners across all technical work packages to ensure comprehensive implementation. Each partner is responsible for monitoring the sources that are more appropriate for its interest, i.e., market watch, patent watch, and standardization tracking.

1.2 RELATION TO OTHER TASKS AND DELIVERABLES

The present deliverable includes the definition of the Exploitable Outcomes of the project so far, and the Individual Exploitation Plan. The second and final version of the deliverable (D6.3) will provide the complete Business Plan and all the exploitable outcomes of the project.

Task 6.3 - Dissemination & Exploitation Activities

The tables below showcases the social media KPI’s, the publications and the events that OASEES has participated.

Social Media KPIs

Platform	Impressions	Followers/Users	Reactions	Engagement Time
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LinkedIn	27461	284	1534	-
Twitter	3821	279	-	-
Website	14802	1328	-	1m 50s

- **Publications**

Publications Table

Partner	Name of Journal	Topics	URL
NKUA, NCSR D	ARES '23: Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security	Availability, Reliability and Security	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3600160.3605088
NCSR D, OTE (Paper "Energy Efficiency in Agriculture through Tokenization of 5G and Edge Applications")	Energies	Networks, Blockchain	https://doi.org/10.3390/en16135182
NCSR D (Paper "Neuromorphic computing based on halide perovskites ")	Nature Electronics	Electronics, SNN	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41928-023-01082-z

- Events

Events Table

Description	Section	Link
AIAI-2023 Conference - The 8th 5G-PINE Workshop (Workshop organization)	Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations	https://ifipaiai.org/2023/
3rd International Workshop on Advances on Privacy Preserving Technologies and Solutions	Availability, Reliability and Security	https://www.ares-conference.eu/workshops/iwaps-2023/
UNified 2023 International Conference of DAMAS IncoME and TEPEN Conferences	AI in future 6G communications and wireless sensor networks	https://unified2023.org/
25th InfoCom World Conference Diginvest in Greece: New Horizons	Telecommunications and ICT	https://infocomworld.gr/en/
E-CHARGE SHOW	Energy sector, eMobility sector	https://e-charge.show/
KEY - Italian Exhibition Group	Energy sector, eMobility sector	https://www.key-expo.com/
VTM - Vehicle & Transportation Meetings	Energy sector, eMobility sector	https://italy.vehiclemeetings.com/index.php

Related Deliverable Table

Deliverable	Lead Partner	PU/CO	Due Date
D6.3 Exploitation and Standardization Activities	TEC	Public	M36

1.3 METHODOLOGY

1.3.1 IDENTIFICATION OF EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

In the first 12 months, the OASEES partners have identified the exploitable assets of the project, following the guidelines of the Grant Agreement (GA). This process involved a systematic assessment of project outputs to ascertain their potential for exploitation, identifying key results crucial for achieving project objectives and maximizing impact.

Exploitable assets encompass a broad range of outcomes or results generated within the project with potential for exploitation. Examples of primary categories of possible exploitable assets include:

- **Intellectual Property:** This includes patents, copyrights, or trademarks that can be legally protected and commercialized.
- **Technological Innovation:** Encompassing technologies, products, services, or solutions that bring about innovation in their respective domains.
- **Architectural Design:** Referring to frameworks, architectures, or blueprints that serve as foundational structures for various applications.
- **Data Assets:** Covering datasets, databases, or knowledge bases with valuable information for research or commercial purposes.
- **Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning:** Involving Artificial Intelligence (AI) / Machine Learning (ML) models that offer advanced computational capabilities for diverse applications.
- **Policy and Standardization:** Encompassing policies, guidelines, recommendations, or contributions to standardization efforts in a particular field.
- **Educational Resources:** Including training materials, manuals, courses, or presentations that facilitate knowledge transfer and learning.
- **Methodological Tools:** Encompassing techniques, processes, or methodologies that provide systematic approaches to problem-solving or project execution.

1.3.2 ANALYSIS OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

The analysis of the intellectual property rights is associated with the Key Exploitable Results identified in the previous section. Intellectual Property Rights analysis is important for protecting research and innovation outcomes. Identification and analysis of each KER is pivotal and must be defined and agreed from each involved partner. Through the Consortium Agreement partners agree for each KER.

1.3.3 IDENTIFICATION OF EXPLOITATION TYPES & PATHWAYS

M – Market: Partner wishes/offers opportunity to Sell by using their pre-existing sales channels to promote to potential client networks the asset (Ownership of asset not necessary, partner may request permission to sell through license agreement from another partner who owns the asset). This is Selling intention.

C – Technical Creation, Assembly, Production: Partner wishes to produce the asset (irrespective if they will sell it alone or through 3rd parties channels). This is the technical development intention.

L – License: Partner wishes to consider opportunities to License/Assign their asset or knowledge on the asset, to 3rd parties that wish to exploit it, for an agreed fee (Typical for Universities without Sales Force)

I - Internal: Partner foresees opportunities for Internal use and expansion or replication in the future (Typical for Pilots, Demonstrators, Factories etc.), also adoption in company product lines

R – Research: Research Further – Journal/Conference Publications/ other research initiatives

P – Publish: Handbooks, Best-Practices, Presentations, Multimedia/Videos, Books, Charts etc.

D – Dataset: Partner can exploit datasets of the particular asset through online marketplaces, for experiments, for further research, for consulting services etc.

T – Training: Partner wishes to produce Training Material and/or offer Training Services/ Methods (online test, webinar, printed, other) related to the asset.

S - Services: Partner willing to provide Services (complementing the asset) such as Consulting, Lectures, Technical Integration, Support, Maintenance, other Added Value Services around the main asset.

G – Governmental: Partner has links and can promote Assets to Governmental/EC Policy Recommendations or make contributions to Standardization Bodies and Associations.

1.3.4 BUSINESS MODELS AND MARKET ANALYSIS

After the identification of the exploitable assets, we focus on developing business models and conducting a market analysis for each exploitable outcome. A strategy is outlined with emphasis in target audience, value proposition and revenue streams. The tools used to depict and analyse the business models are the Business Model Canvas (BMC), Value Proposition Canvas (VPC), and SWOT analysis.

Business Model Canvas (BMC) Template

Business Model Canvas

Value Proposition Canvas (VPC) Template

1.4 TABLE OF EXPLOITABLE ASSETS

This section of the deliverable includes the table of the exploitable assets and its abbreviations.

Abbreviations Table

F-Framework/Architecture/Blueprint/Guideline
M-Module/Platform Element/Side Product
D-Dataset/Knowledge Base
P-Pilot/Use Case/Application
I-Intangible/Patent/Publication

Exploitable Assets Table

a/a	Asset Title	Source of Asset	Introduced by Partner	Related to Pilot	Category
F	OASEES Platform	Pilot integration	All	1,5,6	Architecture
M	Technical Reports	Robotic use case	Robotnik	5	Side Product
D	Anonymized Data	Furniture production data	Robotnik, SCM	5	Dataset
P	OASEES DAO & Dapp	OASEES Portal	InfraChain, Robotnik	5	Application
P	Robotic Swarm powered Smart Factory for I4.0	Automated furniture production	Robotnik, SCM	5	Pilot
M	Patient pathology severity detection algorithms	Recordings of voice	CEA	1	Module
M	Technical Reports	Health use case data and results	CEA/Hopale	1	Side Product
M	Re-education plan	Health use case data and results	CEA/Hopale	1	Side Product
D	Anonymized Data	Speech data	Hopale	1	Dataset
P	OASEES DAO & DAPP for the Health Use Case	OASEES Portal	CEA & InfraChain	1	Application

P	Smart Edge-Connected Node for the Analysis of Voice, Articulation and Fluency disorders in Parkinson Disease	Parkinson patient reeducation	CEA/Hopale/InfraChain/ Demokritos	1	Pilot
I	Severity assessment and reeducation of dysarthric voice in Parkinson patients	Development and results from use case	CEA/Hopale	1	Publication
M	Anomaly Detection Algorithms	Wind turbine data and IoT Device data	Capgemini	6	Module
M	Predictive Algorithms	Wind turbine data and IoT Device data	Capgemini	6	Module
M	Technical Reports	Wind turbine data, IoT Device data and algorithm results	Capgemini	6	Side Product
M	Dynamic Maintenance Plan & LCOE	Wind turbine data, IoT Device data, algorithm results	Capgemini	6	Side Product
D	Anonymized Data	Wind turbine data and IoT Device data	Capgemini & Tecnalia	6	Dataset
P	OASEES DAO & DAPP	OASEES Portal	Capgemini & InfraChain	6	Application

P	Smart Swarm Energy harvesting and Predictive Maintenance Wind turbines	Wind Turbine Maintenance	Capgemini	6	Pilot
I	System and procedure for detecting irregularities in wind turbine blades	Blade Acoustic Monitoring System	Capgemini	6	Patent
I	Non-intrusive detection of wind turbine blade faults through collaborative swarm collaboration using acoustic data from the blades	Development and results from use case	Capgemini & Adrestia	6	Publication
M	Technical Reports	SCM Use Case	SCM GROUP	5	Side Product
P	Robotic Swarm - Smart Factory I4.0	Collaborative robotic automation for sanding process	SCM GROUP, ROBOTNIK	5	Use Case
	OASEES SDK and Lifecycle Management	Own developments	SPH	ALL	Module/Platform element
M	Blockchain Based Broker	Development & Gaia-X surveillance	TECNALIA	N/A	Module/Platform element
I	SSI enabled ABE	Research	TECNALIA	N/A	Publication

M	Gaia-X Onboarding API	Gaia-X API Library generated in DATAMITE European Project developed by Tecnia	TECNALIA	ALL	Module
D	Energy production and consumption data	Power distribution network (City of Terni)	ASMT	2	Dataset
I	Publication for 5G High Mast Inspection based on DAO	Development and results from use case	OTE, NCRCD, IMEC	3	Publication
P	Connectivity as a Service	Pilot Integration	OTE	3	Pilot
M	OASEES edge node, 5G RAN components	Pilot Integration	OTE	3	Platform element
P	Drone swarm over 5G for high mast inspection	Autonomous drone inspections over 5G	OTE, NCSR, IMEC	3	Use case

2. EXPLOITABLE OUTCOMES

In the section of the deliverable a detailed business plan of each exploitable outcome is showcased by each partner involved in the exploitable outcomes.

2.1 EXPLOITABLE OUTCOME #1 – ASM TERNI

Table 1 : Exploitable Outcome #1

Owner	ASMT – As DSO, ASMT is the owner of the datasets used to generate the energy forecasting and, consequently, the flexibility bids on the digital marketplace.
Contributors	DST (owner of the energy production and forecasting module)
Ownership per Implementation	N/A
Protection Measures	NDA with the technology provider
Usage Rights	N/A
Licensing Information	N/A
Notes	N/A

2.1.1 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

This section will provide the BMC analysis.

Table 2 : BMC Analysis Ex. Out. #1

Key Partners	Role
ASM Terni	DSO
EMOTION	CPO/EMSP/EV Fleet Manager
DST	Technical solution developer
Other OASEES Partners	Developer of OASEES platform and DAO
Forecasting of energy flows	ASMT will leverage on an energy production and consumption forecast (developed by DST) in order to assess the entity of Reverse Power Flow (RPF) in the distribution grid a day ahead
Flexibility bid generation	ASMT will generate one or more energy flexibility bids on the digital marketplace (developed by DST) corresponding to the foreseen time and entity of the RPF
Flexibility trade	EMOTION and other EV fleet managers or other EV users will plan and shift their consumption (EV charging) flexibility in order to accommodate ASMT request, thus participating in the bidding
Flexibility acceptance	ASMT will accept the best offer(s) and the EV charging will be scheduled at the time needed to relieve the power grid of the RPF.

Energy historical and real time data from ASMT	Data from ASMT managed distribution grid, including loads and power generation plants (usually PVs) in the energy district considered, as well as weather forecasting data.
Forecasting service	Energy forecasting service based on such data. It aims at foresee the imbalance between local generation and consumption
Digital marketplace	A block-chain based digital marketplace, where ASMT can auction the energy surplus foreseen at a discounted price, seeking EV users to exploit their flexibility accordingly.
CPOs charging info for eMSPs	A data product exchanged among DSO and other actors of e-mobility
EVs fleet coordinated recharging to support optimal operation of electricity grid	A Use Case that allow the power electricity grid manager to avoid costly upgrades, using the charging flexibility offered by e-mobility in moments of temporary energy production surplus
Enhancement overall efficiency of PV production	The increased local exploitation accommodated through EV flexibility allows for a better exploitation of PV generated energy. There will be less energy dissipated as it would have been by flowing from one energy district upward (RPF) to high voltage grid to be consumed in another energy district
Discounted EV charging	The EV fleet managers and general EV users will be able to charge their EV at a discounted rate at EV charging station within specific location and times, provided they win the bidding.
Channels	Description
Digital marketplace	The DSO will communicate with EMSPs and fleet managers through the digital marketplace
EMSPs apps	Generic EV users might be able to participate to bidding through their EMSP app
Customer Segments	Description
Distribution system operators	DSOs will avoid costly upgrades of the infrastructures to deal with intermittent energy surplus
e-mobility	EV users and EV fleet managers will benefit from discounted-rate charging
Forecasting services	DSO needs to acquire and maintain an energy forecasting service
Digital marketplace fees	The digital marketplace will be created and maintained
EV charging discounts	The winning EV users will recharge with some monetary incentives
Reduction in distribution system upgrades	The DSO will avoid costly upgrades of the distribution grid

Table 3 : BMC Ex. Out. #1

Business Model Canvas	Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
	Energy consumers	ASMT	03/04/2024	V.01
<p><u>Key Partners</u></p> <p>Consortium partners of OASEES SW providers CPOs EV fleet Managers DSO</p> <p>MOTIVATIONS FOR PARTNERSHIPS:</p> <p>Improving power network stability</p> <p>Reduction of risk of faults Acquisition of know-how and technologies for smartening the power distribution network</p>	<p><u>Key Activities</u></p> <p>Energy data gathering, monetary and non-monetary incentive mechanisms design,</p> <p>CATEGORIES:</p> <p>Data gathering, data analytics,</p>	<p><u>Value Propositions</u></p> <p>Power network stability and resilience Maximisation of the use of green energy produced locally, avoiding RPF Attract EV drivers thanks to the relationship with the local CPOs Discounted EV charging</p>	<p><u>Customer Relationships</u></p> <p>It is expected that DSOs and EV CPOs exchange data and information to facilitate grid management and optimize charging operations.</p>	<p><u>Customer Segments</u></p> <p>CPOs and EV Drivers DSO</p>
	<p><u>Key Resources</u></p> <p>Smart edge devices (i.d. Smart Meters, PMUs, LV SCADA) Dedicated AI algorithms</p> <p>TYPES OF RESOURCES:</p> <p>HW, SW, data availability, EV users and financial resources patents, copyrights, data), Human, Financial</p>	<p>CHARACTERISTICS:</p> <p>Performance, customisation, cost reduction of the EV charging, risk reduction of fault in the LV/MV grid</p>	<p><u>Channels</u></p> <p>Direct and indirect communication; Digital marketplace EMSPs App</p>	

<p><u>Cost Structure</u> External services (SaaS, technology development, etc.) IS YOUR BUSINESS MORE: Value Driven SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS: Fixed Costs</p>	<p><u>Revenue Streams</u> Costs saving due to the reduction of congestion in the grid. TYPES: Usage fee FIXED PRICING: Customer segment dependent DYNAMIC PRICING: Negotiation (bargaining), Yield Management, Real-time-Market</p>
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2.1.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

This section will provide the SWOT analysis.

Table 4 : SWOT Analysis Ex. Out. #1

<p>S Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accuracy improvements: energy forecasting tools have improved significantly with the advancements in machine learning and data analytics. • Cost efficiency: this business avoids costly upgrades of power grids by simply leveraging on already existing assets’ flexibility • Operational efficiency: by predicting energy demand, DSO can optimize its operations, such as scheduling maintenance activities and allocating resources efficiently. • Environmental benefits: better exploitation of renewable energy stream thus reducing carbon footprint. 	<p>W Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data dependency: inaccurate or insufficient data can lead to less reliable forecasts • Model inaccuracy, especially when intermittent generation is considered. • Resource constraints, in terms of investment in technology (HW and SW) especially for small DSO • Low awareness of consumers (e.g. EV users) to participate to flexibility biddings. Small monetary incentives alone might not be very attractive
<p>O Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster RES penetration due to the forecasting modules able to overcome intermittency and variability of renewable generation. • Market Innovation: different actors with energy consumption flexibility could be involved in the digital marketplace auction systems 	<p>T Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delays in regulatory framework on peer-to-peer energy trading • Cybersecurity threats may pose a significant risk to energy forecasting systems, potentially compromising data integrity and system reliability • Changes in energy prices, demand patterns, or the emergence of new market entrants can pose threats to the forecasting capabilities and market position.

2.1.3 VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

Table 5 : VPC Analysis Ex. Out. #1

Benefits	Description	Wants	Description
Overload reduction in the LV/MV network through a demand supply balancing	By using the energy forecasting module and the marketplace auction, the DSO can balance the grid attracting at specific locations and time energy consumers, like EV drivers		
		Avoid costly upgrades of the grid	Instead of dealing with costly upgrades of the grid to deal with increased penetration of RES generated energy, the DSO will be able to just auction the surplus of energy, after having it forecasted
		Avoid Reverse Power Flows due to the unbalanced production and generation	The DSO will manage to keep the consumption of PV generated energy local, avoiding dissipation of that energy while flowing in RPF
Features	Description	Needs	Description
Digital marketplace auction	The DSO will place an auction on the marketplace and EV users and fleet managers will bid in order to win discounted charging fees at specific locations and times	Energy consumers require a reliable supply of electricity and affordable energy prices, as well as minimise the environmental impact	Energy reliability, affordability, sustainability, convenience, community engagement are the main needs of the energy consumers.

		reducing their carbon footprint	
Energy forecasting module	A ML based forecasting services, to be available for DSO daily needs		
Experience	Description	Fears	Description
The DSO participates to energy marketplace auction generating bids and accepting the best offers received from the consumers (e.g. EV fleet managers)	The DSO generates one or more energy flexibility bids on the digital marketplace. Consumers, like CPOs and other EV fleet managers or other EV users plan and shift their consumption (EV charging) flexibility in order to accommodate DSO request, thus participating in the bidding. The DSO accepts the best offer(s) and the EV charging will be scheduled at the time needed to relieve the power grid of the RPF.	Not being able to fulfil the promised charging in case of unexpected disruption of their schedule	Inaccurate energy data, unforeseen events like weather condition, natural disasters, or geopolitical disruptions can significantly impact energy supply and demand, making it difficult to accurately forecast energy production and consumption. Moreover, problems with data collection, storage, processing, or analysis can introduce errors into the forecasting process.
Ideal Customer	Description	Substitutes	Description
Energy consumers (e.g. EV fleet operator, EV users)	Every energy consumer able to exploit the energy flexibility provided by the DSO. For instance, the manager of a EV fleet which is able to exploit the discount charging rates to generate relevant savings for their company		
		Alternative methods to balance energy production and	The energy customer might choose other methods than the use of

	consumption in the distribution grid, like advanced DR programs, energy storage penetration and energy communities' creation.
	the marketplace for selling their flexibility

Table 6 : VPC Ex. Out. #1

		<i>Designed for:</i>	<i>Designed by:</i>	<i>Date:</i>	<i>Version:</i>
Value Proposition Canvas		Energy consumers	ASMT	03/04/2024	V.01
Benefits Overload reduction in the LV/MV network through a demand supply balancing.	Experience The DSO participates to energy marketplace auction generating bids and accepting the best offers received from the energy consumers (e.g. EV fleet managers)		Wants Avoid costly upgrades of the grid Avoid Reverse Power Flows due to the unbalanced production and generation.	Fears Inaccurate energy forecasting due to data inaccuracy and other unforeseen events	
Features Based on the results of the energy forecasting module, the DSO generates one or more energy flexibility bids on the digital marketplace.			Needs Energy consumers require a reliable supply of electricity and affordable energy prices, as well as minimise their carbon footprint.		
Product	Ideal Customer	Substitutes			

Energy forecasting for generating flexibility bids on the digital marketplace	Energy consumers (e.g. EV fleet operator, EV users)	Alternative methods to balance energy production and consumption in the distribution grid, like advanced DR programs, energy storage penetration and energy communities' creation.
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2.2 EXPLOITABLE OUTCOME #2 – AXON LOGIC

Table 7 : Exploitable Outcome #2

Owner	Axon logic is working closely with SENSO for developing both classical and quantum machine learning solutions in USE CASE 4
Contributors	<p>SENSO: Provide collected data</p> <p>Axon logic : Creating LSTM/QLSTM and integrating Matrix Product State with LSTM, alongside other feasible quantum convolutional networks, for tasks such as regression prediction or classification.</p> <p>Testing a hybrid quantum reinforcement learning for computing data rate in a UAV system that may be used in the USE CASE “Drone swarm over 5g for high mast inspection”</p>
Ownership per Implementation	N/A
Protection Measures	<p>Authorships</p> <p>Possible Open-source derived business model</p>
Usage Rights	Available for partners in the context and duration of the project
Licensing Information	No licensing terms yet. Possibly Open-Source
Notes	N/A

2.2.1 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Table 8 : BMC Analysis Ex. Out. #2

Key Partners	Role
OASEES Partners	OASEES platform development
Infrachain, Demokritos	DAO
Axon	Quantum computing and integration to SENSO’s systems

Key Activities	Description
Studying seismic sensor data collected by SENSO	Investigate the correlation between features.
Converting the classical data into quantum data	Looking for a suitable data encoding method
Looking for hybrid classical-quantum solution	Quantum computer is still in its infancy stage, hybrid model is considered
Compare the performance of prediction between dress circuit technique to tensor network	Both techniques are used to reduce the total number of input features to fit into variational circuit networks.
Key Resources	Description
Forecasting service	Assist SENSO for decision making based on the given data
Value Propositions	Description
Provide an alternative way i.e. quantum approach for developing reliable seismic event decision making system	From the state-of-art research, most of the results show that quantum machine learning show better performance than classical ones.
Customer Relationships	Description
Forming cooperative alliances with consortium partners, stakeholders, and end-users involved in the utilization of use cases.	Building robust connections via effective communication, teamwork, and ongoing interaction to guarantee harmony with project objectives and fulfill stakeholder requirements.
Channels	Description
Utilizing project meetings, workshops, conferences, online collaboration platforms, and dedicated communication channels for project coordination.	Employing diverse channels to facilitate efficient communication, collaboration, and distribution of project activities, progress, and outcomes
Asset owners	Owners or managers of valuable structural assets
Safety and security management of assets	People responsible with the safety and security of the asset and personnel
Customer Segments	Description
Collaborative partners, end-users, and stakeholders within the domains of decentralized edge computing, IoT, and identity management.	Working closely with partners who embrace the quantum solution
Cost Structure	Description
Personnel (R&D cost, personnel expenses, infrastructure costs, and other operational costs)	Assigning resources and budget for research, development, testing, validation, project management, and collaborative endeavors within the framework of the OASEES project.
Revenue Streams	Description
Project funding from the European Union, and potential to promote the feasibility of quantum solution	Clients may have interest to try the quantum solution in the near future that anticipated yielding much better .performance

Table 9 : BMC Ex. Out. #2

Business Model Canvas	Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
	Earthquake Safety Planners for SENSO via quantum approach	Axon logic	10.04.2024	v1.0
<p><u>Key Partners</u> Consortium partners of the OASEES project, especially SENSO</p> <p>MOTIVATIONS FOR PARTNERSHIPS: Optimization and economy, Reduction of risk and uncertainty, Acquisition of particular resources and activities.</p>	<p><u>Key Activities</u> Provide solutions for both classical and quantum approach</p> <p>CATEGORIES: Development, Implementation, testing and validation</p> <p><u>Key Resources</u> Expertise in the application of quantum algorithms in ICT area.</p> <p>TYPES OF RESOURCES: Physical, Intellectual (brand patents, copyrights, data), Human, Financial</p>	<p><u>Value Propositions</u> CHARACTERISTIC S: Newness, Performance, Customization, “Getting the Job Done”, Design, Brand/Status, Price, Cost Reduction, Risk Reduction, Accessibility, Convenience/Usability</p>	<p><u>Customer Relationships</u> Collaborative partnerships with consortium partners, stakeholders, and end-users of the use case 4 and use case 3</p> <p><u>Channels</u> Project meetings, workshops, conferences, online collaboration platforms, and project communication channels cost-efficient? How are we integrating them with customer routines?</p>	<p><u>Customer Segments</u> Consortium partners, end-users, stakeholders in the field of decentralized edge computing, IoT.</p>

<p><u>Cost Structure</u> R&D costs, personnel expenses, infrastructure cost?</p> <p>IS YOUR BUSINESS MORE Value Driven</p> <p>SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS: Fixed Costs (salaries, rents, utilities</p>	<p><u>Revenue Streams</u> Project funding from the European Union ?</p> <p>TYPES: Asset sale</p> <p>FIXED PRICING: List Price, Product feature dependent, Customer segment dependent,</p> <p>DYNAMIC PRICING: Real-time-Market</p>
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2.2.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

Table 10 : SWOT Analysis Ex. Out. #2

S	Strengths	W	Weaknesses
	<p>What are your key competencies and strengths?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantum optimization • Quantum data driven approach 		<p>What areas require improvement or show vulnerabilities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May not be able to implement the algorithm in current state-of-art quantum computer
O	Opportunities	T	Threats
	<p>What unique resources or advantages can you leverage?</p> <p>Unique database for SENSO collected data</p>		<p>How do others perceive potential challenges or threats to your organization or project?</p> <p>Very noisy data that causes weak prediction</p>

2.2.3 VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

Table 11 : VPC Analysis Ex.Out. #2

Benefits	Description	Wants	Description
When quantum computer is ready, the model can be trained in very fast time	Quantum solution leads to enjoying the quantum advantage	A very short time for getting precise prediction values compared to classical approach	For earth-quake or under dynamic system, fast and accurate prediction are the major concern

Features		Needs	
Features	Description	Needs	Description
Fast in training an AI model	Enjoy the quantum advantage		
Experience		Fears	
Experience	Description	Fears	Description
Applied QNN in wireless communications via simulations	For computing energy efficient	Training a model be too slow if running in small GPU	Quantum approach needs lots of memory
Applied QLSTM for indoor location detection			
Ideal Customer		Substitutes	
Ideal Customer	Description	Substitutes	Description
N/A		N/A	

Table 12 : VPC Ex. Out. #2

Value Proposition Canvas				Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
Benefits	Experience	Wants	Fears				
Fully quantum approach or hybrid quantum is anticipated to outperform classical solutions significantly.	Recent studies have demonstrated that quantum machine learning algorithms have surpassed classical machine learning in performance..	The system developed by SENSO must be sufficiently fast, as time is crucial, especially in the aftermath of a large earthquake.	For large-scale problems, the quantum approach may not be feasible for implementation due to limitations in computing facilities. Subscribing to a quantum cloud service could be prohibitively expensive."				
Features		Needs					

<p>Typically, quantum/hybrid quantum approaches employ fewer neurons compared to classical ones. This may save lots of memory</p>		<p>N/A.</p>	
<p>Product The product is simply an algorithmic development that draws from both classical and quantum AI."</p>	<p>Ideal Customer Provide alternative solutions for SENSO</p>		<p>Substitutes New types of classical machine algorithms might emerge as alternatives to the quantum approach, given their simpler implementation.</p>

2.3 EXPLOITABLE OUTCOME #3 - CEA

Table 13 : Exploitable Outcome #3

<p>Owner</p>	<p>CEA is the use case leader providing the smart edge device with associated sensors and classification algorithms.</p>
<p>Contributors</p>	<p>HOPALE is providing the pathologic speech data together with annotations and is guiding the severity assessment as well as input on exercises. Demokritos and InfraChain are developing the DAO and secure data exchange for use case 1.</p>
<p>Ownership per Implementation</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Protection Measures</p>	<p>Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) between project partners</p>
<p>Usage Rights</p>	<p>N/A (to be negotiated independently)</p>
<p>Licensing Information</p>	<p>N/A (to be negotiated independently)</p>
<p>Notes</p>	<p>N/A</p>

2.3.1 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Table 14 : BMC Analysis Ex. Out. #3

Key Partners	Role
OASEES partners	OASEES platform
Infracrain, Demokritos	DAO
HOPALE	Data collection, annotation
Key Activities	Description
Voice data recording related to Parkinson's disease	Gathering of recordings of pathological and non-pathological voice with a smart edge device using special exercises and metrics set-up by speech therapists.
Data annotation	Manual data annotation and transcription by speech therapists
Data analytics	Deep learning algorithms (self-supervised learning, transfer learning) are applied to voice data to automatically recognize patterns and features associated with Parkinson's disease. These algorithms can learn from large datasets, identifying subtle variations in voice patterns that may indicate the presence or progression of the disease.
Hardware development and software integration	Design and implementation of the smart edge device with the OASEES platform running on it as well as specialized algorithms for disease assessment.
Key Resources	Description
Health professional	Speech therapists gathering and annotating data as well as providing individual exercises to the patients; follow-up for algorithm and application design.
Software design	Training and adaptation of specialized AI algorithms related to the speech rehabilitation of Parkinson disease patients
Hardware design and implementation	Design and prototyping of the smart edge device to be given to the patients
Value Propositions	Description
Severity assessment system	A data product that not only detects the presence of Parkinson's disease but also assesses its severity. The deep learning model will provide a quantitative measure of disease severity based on specific voice features. This information can assist healthcare professionals in tailoring treatment plans and monitoring disease progression.
Research Database for Voice Biomarkers	A data product that contributes to research by creating a database of voice biomarkers associated with Parkinson's disease. This database could be anonymized and shared with researchers to further explore correlations between specific voice patterns and disease progression, potentially leading to new insights and treatment strategies.

Smart edge device	Smart edge device for Parkinson related speech rehabilitation to be used at home and in rehabilitation centres providing secure and anonymous data exchange.
Customer Relationships	Description
Assessment of disease severity	Assessment of disease severity remains current and reflective of the patient's evolving health status.
Personalized exercise plans	Personalized Exercise Plans: The incorporation of disease severity into exercise planning indicates a personalized treatment strategy. The involvement of speech therapists and their opinions introduces a crucial human element to the decision-making process.
Real-time adaptation of the individual treatment plans	Real-time adaptability enhances the efficiency of the rehabilitation process, allowing for prompt adjustments to the treatment plan as needed.
Channels	Description
Hospitals	Hospitals providing healthcare for neurodegenerative diseases
Individual speech therapists	Speech therapists providing a personalized treatment strategy and follow-up for patients working on disease-related exercises from home.
Customer Segments	Description
Geographic	At distance guidance and follow-up for patients suffering from neuro-degenerative disease to maintain or regain an adequate speech intelligibility level
Demographic	Segmentation in different user groups, mainly the elderly (device must be easy to use) and the detected pathology (Parkinson)
Cost Structure	Description
Hospitals – speech therapists	Hospitals and speech therapists providing personalized rehabilitation related to speech
Software providers	Software infrastructure providers, analytics providers
Hardware providers	Smart edge devices, servers for data storage
Social security and health insurance companies	Partly supporting related charges
Revenue Streams	Description
Per time payments of health professionals	Health professionals are payed using smart contracts able to time-stamp the duration spent on each patient
Per smart edge-device payments	Payments per edge device purchased by health professionals or patients
Per download of DAO and algorithms	Payments based on the use of the OASEES platform and the downloaded algorithm

Table 15 : BMC Ex. Out. #3

Business Model Canvas	Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
	Speech therapists	CEA	16/04/2024	1.0
<p><u>Key Partners</u></p> <p>Speech therapists who are in direct contact with the patients. Primary set-up of the device.</p> <p>Software providers (OASEES platform, AI algorithms, exercise providers)</p> <p>Hardware providers (servers and smart edge device)</p> <p>MOTIVATIONS FOR PARTNERSHIPS:</p> <p>AI Optimization and monetization of algorithms</p>	<p><u>Key Activities</u></p> <p>Devices to be given to patients by hospitals and speech therapists. Payments per device, software version and time spent per patient for follow-up and treatment adaptation.</p> <p>CATEGORIES:</p> <p>Device Production, Data gathering, Analytics adaptation Platform/Network</p>	<p><u>Value Propositions</u></p> <p>Integration of advanced technology and human expertise to personalize and optimize the rehabilitation process for individuals with a specific medical condition, likely related to speech disorders or similar health issues.</p> <p>The value added by this approach lies in the precision, personalization, and responsiveness it brings to the rehabilitation process, optimizing the patient's journey towards recovery.</p> <p>CHARACTERISTICS: Performance, Accessibility,</p>	<p><u>Customer Relationships</u></p> <p>Personalized treatment of patients, close follow-up, increased training time due to self-training at home.</p> <p>This is integrated with a platform where health professionals can access and gather information about the current health state of the individual patient in order to adapt and update related exercises and treatment plans.</p>	<p><u>Customer Segments</u></p> <p>Patients with specific medical conditions affecting speech (Parkinson disease). Most the time, those patients are 60+ years old and need easy to use devices to be able to do the exercises at home.</p>

<p>Acquisition of particular resources and activities.</p> <p>Individualized treatment</p>	<p><u>Key Resources</u></p> <p>OASEES platform for secure data exchange</p> <p>Smart edge device</p> <p>Dedicated algorithms</p> <p>Smart contracts for time-based and download-based payments</p> <p>TYPES OF RESOURCES:</p> <p>Physical, Intellectual (brand patents, copyrights, data), Human,</p>	<p>Convenience/Usability</p>	<p><u>Channels</u></p> <p>Currently, patients are meeting health professionals (i.e. speech therapists) after the initial diagnostic of the disease.</p> <p>Most the time this is on a weekly basis exercising for at most one hour.</p> <p>Home-based training could increase the training time and allow patients with physical or cognitive issues to optimize their journey to recovery.</p>	
<p><u>Cost Structure</u></p> <p>Requires further research in the future.</p>		<p><u>Revenue Streams</u></p> <p>Requires further research in the future.</p>		

2.3.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

Table 16 : SWOT Analysis Ex. Out. #3

S	Strengths	W	Weaknesses
	Severity assessment of specific diseases able to detect any improvement or degradation Quick adaptation of treatment and exercises Increased training-time for patients		Precision of the severity assessment Usability of the device Data protection
O	Opportunities	T	Threats
	Unique database for French Parkinson patients Totally secured data transfer		Appearance of new more powerful algorithms Data leaks (health data is very sensitive data; voice is Personally Identifiable Information)

2.3.3 VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

Table 17 : VPC Analysis Ex.Out. #3

Benefits	Description	Wants	Description
Severity assessment of specific diseases able to detect any improvement or degradation	The health professional needs to be able to get information about the voice disorder evolution	Easy to use device and software interface	The device needs to be used by patients (mostly the elderly) without any problem
Quick adaptation of treatment and exercises	Treatment and exercises can be adapted individually for each patient without physical meeting	Secure data transfer	Voice is Personally Identifiable Information
Increased training-time for patients	Training-time is the key to recover.	Refunded by social security and health insurances	This will allow quick adoption by the health professionals

Features	Description	Needs	Description
Smart edge device	<p>Recording function</p> <p>Loudspeaker function for interaction</p> <p>Exercises</p> <p>Analytics and data transfer</p>	How to improve a patient's social experience when using the application?	Spending more time on individual training should help the patient regain or keep communication skills.
User interface for stakeholders	<p>Health professionals (data representation, exercises adaptation, follow-up, visualisation);</p> <p>Database for deployment of devices and patients (hospitals)</p> <p>Database for retraining and optimisation</p> <p>Algorithms section</p> <p>Hardware providers</p>	How do we help patients to adhere to the prescribed interventions?	Serious games motivating the patient using the system as much as possible.
Serious games (not part of OASEES)	Exercises for speech rehabilitation		
Experience	Description	Fears	Description
To be evaluated		Patient is not accepting the device and the framework because he or she is not aware of the difficulties, not accepting the difficulties.	
		Progression of the disease.	
Ideal Customer	Description	Substitutes	Description
Claire	76 years, diagnosis of Parkinson disease with slight dysarthria	Competitors can design better algorithms.	New deep learning approaches could yield better results.

	Drugs healing neurodegenerative diseases.	Humanity could overcome those diseases with drugs.
	Brain interfaces?	Other ways of communications and locomotion.

Table 18 : VPC Ex. Out. #3

		<i>Designed for:</i>	<i>Designed by:</i>	<i>Date:</i>	<i>Version:</i>
Value Proposition Canvas		Patients with neurodegenerative diseases	CEA, HOPALE, Demokritos, Infrachain	22/03/24	1.0
<p>Benefits</p> <p>Integration of advanced technology and human expertise to personalize and optimize the rehabilitation process for individuals with a specific medical condition, likely related to speech disorders or similar health issues.</p> <p>The value added by this approach lies in the precision, personalization, and responsiveness it brings to the rehabilitation process, optimizing the patient's journey towards</p>	<p>Experience</p> <p>Ideally, we propose an end-to-end solution with personal guidance to the patient provided by the healthcare professional in a remote configuration. The patient selects the time he or she wants to spent on the exercises.</p>	<p>Wants</p> <p>Total recovering with a minimum effort.</p>	<p>Fears</p> <p>Patient is not accepting the device and the framework because he or she is not aware of the difficulties, not accepting the difficulties.</p> <p>Progression of the disease.</p>		

<p>recovery as well as probably an increased training time.</p>			
<p>Features</p> <p>The smart edge device is recording the patient's voice during exercises (using also a loudspeaker and a graphical interface for guidance). This data is analysed and a severity grade is calculated. This is sent to the OASEES platform where the health professional can access the data and adapt the exercises and treatment. Payment is per time spent on the platform.</p>		<p>Needs</p> <p>Spending more time on individual training should help the patient regain or keep communication skills.</p> <p>Serious games motivating the patient using the system as much as possible.</p>	
<p>Product</p> <p>Smart edge device with associated DAO for neurodegenerative disease diagnostic and rehabilitation</p>	<p>Ideal Customer</p> <p>Claire (76 years, diagnosis of Parkinson disease with slight dysarthria)</p>	<p>Substitutes</p> <p>Competitors can design better algorithms.</p> <p>Drugs healing neurodegenerative diseases.</p> <p>Brain interfaces?</p>	

2.4 EXPLOITABLE OUTCOME #4 - EMOTION

Table 19: Exploitable Outcome #4

Owner	EMOTE, as CPO and eMSP, is the owner of the charging station and electric vehicle datasets used to generate the forecasting of potential energy flexibility provision from electric mobility to address DSO needs to balance the electricity grid via a DLT/blockchain decentralized P2P marketplace.
Contributors	DST (owner of the energy flexibility forecasting module and blockchain P2P marketplace)
Ownership per Implementation	N/A
Protection Measures	NDA with the technology provider
Usage Rights	N/A
Licensing Information	N/A
Notes	N/A

2.4.1 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Table 20 : BMC Analysis Ex. Out. #4

Key Partners	Role
EMOTION	CPO/EMSP/EV Fleet Manager
ASM Terni	DSO
DST	Technical solution developer
Other OASEES Partners	Developer of OASEES platform and DAO
Key Activities	Description
Forecasting of EV potential flexibility provision	EMOT will leverage on a EV potential flexibility provision forecast (developed by DST) in order to assess the entity of flexibility energy that could be provided by electric vehicles to DSO
Flexibility trade	EMOTION and other EV fleet managers or other EV users will plan and shift their consumption (EV charging) in order to accommodate DSO request, thus participating in the bidding
Key Resources	Description
Energy historical and real time data from EMOT	Data from EMOT charging stations and electric vehicles
Forecasting service	Energy forecasting service based on such data. It aims at foresee the EV fleet State-of-Charge levels
Digital marketplace	A block-chain based digital marketplace, where EMOT can sell its flexibility by smart charging electric vehicles of the fleet.

Value Propositions	Description
CPOs charging info for eMSPs	A data product exchanged among DSO and other actors of e-mobility
EVs fleet coordinated recharging to support optimal operation of electricity grid	A Use Case that allow the electric mobility service provider to attract more EV users to its charging station and increase its business.
Customer Relationships	Description
Discounted EV charging	The EV fleet managers and general EV users will be able to charge their EV at a discounted rate at EV charging station within specific location and times, provided they win the bidding.
Channels	Description
Digital marketplace	The eMSP will communicate with DSOs and fleet managers through the digital marketplace
EMSPs apps	Generic EV users might be able to participate to bidding through their EMSP app
Customer Segments	Description
Distribution system operators	DSOs will avoid costly upgrades of the infrastructures to deal with intermittent energy surplus
e-mobility	EV users and EV fleet managers will benefit from discounted-rate charging
Cost Structure	Description
Forecasting services	eMSP needs to acquire and maintain an energy forecasting service
Digital marketplace fees	The digital marketplace will be created and maintained
EV charging discounts	The winning EV users will recharge with some monetary incentives
Revenue Streams	Description
Increase EV charging business	The eMSP will attract more EV users to its charging station and increase its business.

Table 21 : BMC Ex. Out. #4

Business Model Canvas	Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
	EV Users	EMOTE	03/04/2024	V.01

<u>Key Partners</u>	<u>Key Activities</u>	<u>Value Propositions</u>	<u>Customer Relationships</u>	<u>Customer Segments</u>
<p>Consortium partners of OASEES eMSPs CPOs EV fleet Managers DSO</p> <p>MOTIVATIONS FOR PARTNERSHIPS:</p> <p>Reduce EV charging energy costs</p> <p>Increase renewable energy usage for EV charging</p>	<p>Energy data gathering (EV SoC), monetary and non monetary incentive mechanisms design</p> <p>CATEGORIES:</p> <p>Data gathering, data analytics</p> <p><u>Key Resources</u></p> <p>Smart meters</p> <p>Charging stations equipped with single-board computer</p> <p>Electric Vehicles equipped with On-board Diagnostic (OBD) IoT Device</p> <p>AI algorithms (ML models)</p> <p>Blockchain-based marketplace</p> <p>TYPES OF RESOURCES:</p> <p>HW, SW, data availability, EV users and financial</p>	<p>What value do we deliver to the customer? Which one of our customer’s problems are we helping to solve? What bundles of products and services are we offering to each Customer Segment? Which customer needs are we satisfying?</p> <p>CHARACTERISTICS : Newness, Performance, Customization, “Getting the Job Done”, Design, Brand/Status, Price, Cost Reduction, Risk Reduction, Accessibility, Convenience/Usability</p>	<p>EV users and eMSPs exchange data and information to satisfy DSO needs related to grid balancing</p> <p><u>Channels</u></p> <p>Direct and indirect communication;</p> <p>Digital marketplace</p> <p>EMSPs App</p>	<p>eMSPs</p> <p>CPOs</p> <p>EV fleet Managers</p> <p>DSO</p>

<u>Cost Structure</u>	<u>Revenue Streams</u>
<p>External services (SaaS, technology development, etc.)</p> <p>IS YOUR BUSINESS MORE: Value Driven .</p> <p>SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS: Fixed Costs</p>	<p>Cost saving due to energy flexibility provision</p> <p>TYPES: Usage fee</p> <p>FIXED PRICING: Customer segment dependent</p> <p>DYNAMIC PRICING: Negotiation (bargaining), Yield Management, Real-time-Market</p>

2.4.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

Table 21 : SWOT Analysis Ex. Out. #4

S	Strengths	W	Weaknesses
	<p>What are your key competencies and strengths?</p> <p>This Business increase eMSP attractiveness by simply leveraging on already existing assets' flexibility</p> <p>It allows for a better exploitation of eMSP charging stations.</p>		<p>What areas require improvement or show vulnerabilities?</p> <p>Need to find a way to interest the EV users to participate to flexibility biddings. Small monetary incentives alone might not be very attractive.</p>
O	Opportunities	T	Threats
	<p>What unique resources or advantages can you leverage?</p> <p>In the future, also other actors with energy consumption flexibility could be involved in the digital marketplace auction system and transition to renewable energies and electric mobility will require less upgrade costs.</p>		<p>How do others perceive potential challenges or threats to your organization or project?</p> <p>Delays in regulatory framework on peer-to-peer energy trading.</p>

2.4.3 VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

Table 22 : VPC Analysis Ex.Out. #4

Benefits	Description	Wants	Description
Discounted rate for EV charging	EV fleet managers and users will get interesting incentives to charge at the specific bid location and time	Exploit the discounted charging rates	The EV user can check a day ahead if any bidding from DSO is available in places and at times compatible with their personal schedule; the EV fleet manager can even plan to re-plan their charging location and times according to the bidding
EVs fleet coordinated recharging to support optimal operation of electricity grid	DSO leverages on e-mobility flexibility to absorb surplus of PV generated energy	Avoid costly upgrades of the grid	Instead of dealing with costly upgrades of the grid to deal with increased penetration of RES generated energy, the DSO will be able to just auction the surplus of energy, after having it forecasted
Energy forecasting for grid and electric mobility	Energy production and consumption forecasting of an energy district based on both historical and real time data from the grid sensors and loads/energy plants. EV flexibility provision forecasting based on both historical and real time data from on-board diagnostic devices installed in the electric vehicles.	Assess a day ahead the possibility of Reverse Power Flows and EV potential flexibility provision	The DSO will manage to keep the consumption of PV generated energy local, avoiding dissipation of that energy while flowing in RPF
Features	Description	Needs	Description
Digital marketplace auction	The DSO will place an auction on the marketplace and EV users and fleet managers	Digital marketplace platform	A block-chain based digital marketplace that will make bidding

	will bid in order to win discounted charging fees at specific locations and times		transparent and safe
Energy forecasting module	A ML based forecasting services, to be available for DSO and eMSP daily needs	ML based forecasting	A ML based forecasting services, to be available for DSO and eMSP daily needs
Experience	Description	Fears	Description
The Ev user/fleet manager participating to energy marketplace auctions.	The Ev user/fleet manager check a day ahead if there is a bid on the Marketplace compatible with their own need and charging capability. They participate to the bid and will be notified in case of victory. The next day, they will recharge at discounted rate	Not being able to fulfil the promised charging in case of unexpected disruption of their schedule	A mechanism might be added for the DSO to ask back compensations in case the promised charging is not actuated by the winner of the bid, in which case EV users may become more aware of participating to auction market
Ideal Customer	Description	Substitutes	Description
EV fleet manager	The manager of a EV fleet, which is able to exploit the discount charging rates to generate relevant savings for their company	Regular charging schedule	The Ev fleet manager might simply ignore the auctions and charge in places and at times convenient for the managing of their fleet
EV user	The EV user checks a day in advance if a bid is available for a time, place and entity of energy compatible with their schedule (e.g. near their workplace during office hours). If they win the bid, they charge at reduce costs without substantial alteration of their schedule	Charging at home or at public place without scheduling	The EV owner might simply charge at his usual location and time paying the regular price if the auctioned slots are not convenient for them.

Table 23 : VPC Ex. Out. #4

Value Proposition Canvas		Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
		EV users	EMOTE	03/04/2024	V.01
Benefits	Experience	Wants	Fears		
Discounted rate for EV charging	The Ev user participating to energy marketplace auctions for energy flexibility provision.	Exploit the discounted charging rates	Not being able to fulfil the promised charging in case of unexpected disruption of their schedule		
Features		Needs			
The DSO will place an auction on the marketplace and EV users will bid in order to win discounted charging fees at specific locations and times		Digital marketplace platform			
Product	Ideal Customer	Substitutes			
Energy flexibility marketplace based on blockchain to enable cooperation between electric grid and electric mobility	EV users	Charging at home or at public place without scheduling			

2.5 EXPLOITABLE OUTCOME #5 - INQBIT

Table 25 : Exploitable Outcome #5

Owner	InQbit Innovations SRL
Contributors	N/A
Ownership per Implementation	N/A
Protection Measures	Authorship
	Industrial Property
	Possible Open-Source derived business model
Usage Rights	Available for partners in the context and duration of the project
Licensing Information	No licensing terms yet. Possibly Open-Source
Notes	N/A

2.5.1 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Table 26 : BMC Analysis Ex. Out. #5

Key Partners	Role
Consortium partners of the OASEES project	Collaboration in designing and implementing the secure, decentralized edge ecosystem with native device support for SSI integration.
Key Activities	Description
Research, development, and implementation of SSI-based solutions for decentralized edge ecosystems	Designing and developing the technical infrastructure, integrating SSI technology, testing and validation through the use cases, and contributing to the dissemination of project results.
Key Resources	Description
Expertise in ICT solutions, cybersecurity services, SSI background technology, research and engineering capabilities	Utilizing the expertise and background of the research and technical team to develop innovative solutions.
Value Propositions	Description
Providing secure, trustworthy, and decentralized edge ecosystems with SSI integration, fulfilling the requirements of persistence, global resolvability, cryptographic verifiability, and decentralization	Offering cutting-edge solutions that address the emerging needs of decentralized edge computing and identity management in line with the objectives of the OASEES project.
Customer Relationships	Description
Collaborative partnerships with consortium partners, stakeholders, and end-users of the use cases	Establishing strong relationships through communication, collaboration, and continuous

	engagement to ensure alignment with project goals and meet the needs of stakeholders.
Channels	Description
Project meetings, workshops, conferences, online collaboration platforms, and project communication channels	Utilizing various channels for effective communication, collaboration, and dissemination of project activities, progress, and results.
Customer Segments	Description
Consortium partners, end-users, stakeholders in the field of decentralized edge computing, IoT, and identity management	Targeting partners and stakeholders who are interested in or affected by the development and implementation of decentralized edge ecosystems with SSI integration for Identity Management.
Cost Structure	Description
Research and development costs, personnel expenses, infrastructure costs, and other operational costs	Allocating resources and budget for research, development, testing, validation, project management, and collaboration activities within the scope of the OASEES project.
Revenue Streams	Description
Project funding from the European Union, and potential revenue from commercialization of developed solutions	Generating revenue through project funding, and potential commercialization of intellectual property beyond the project scope.

Table 27 : BMC Ex. Out. #5

Business Model Canvas	Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
	OASEES Project	InQbit Innovations SRL	30/04/2024	1.0
<u>Key Partners</u> Consortium partners of the OASEES project MOTIVATIONS FOR PARTNERSHIPS: Optimization and economy, Reduction of risk and uncertainty, Acquisition of	<u>Key Activities</u> Research, development, and implementation of SSI-based solutions for decentralized edge ecosystems. CATEGORIES: Development, Implementation, testing and validation	<u>Value Propositions</u> Providing secure, trustworthy, and decentralized edge ecosystems with SSI integration, fulfilling the requirements of persistence, global resolvability, cryptographic verifiability, and decentralization	<u>Customer Relationships</u> Collaborative partnerships with consortium partners, stakeholders, and end-users of the use cases.	<u>Customer Segments</u> Consortium partners, end-users, stakeholders in the field of decentralized edge computing, IoT, and identity management.

<p>particular resources and activities.</p>	<p><u>Key Resources</u></p> <p>Expertise in ICT solutions, cybersecurity services, SSI background technology, research, and engineering capabilities</p> <p>TYPES OF RESOURCES: Physical, Intellectual, Human, Financial</p>	<p>CHARACTERISTIC S: Newness, Performance, Customization, Risk Reduction, Accessibility, Convenience/Usability</p>	<p><u>Channels</u></p> <p>Project meetings, workshops, conferences, online collaboration platforms, and project communication channels</p>	
<p><u>Cost Structure</u></p> <p>Research and development costs, personnel expenses, infrastructure costs</p>		<p><u>Revenue Streams</u></p> <p>Project funding from the European Union, and potential revenue from commercialization of developed solutions</p> <p>TYPES: Asset sale, Advertising</p> <p>FIXED PRICING: List Price, Product feature dependent, Customer segment dependent</p>		

2.5.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

Table 28 : SWOT Analysis Ex. Out. #5

S Strengths	W Weaknesses
<p>What are your key competencies and strengths?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate the strengths of IQB Innovations based on its key resources, capabilities, and value propositions outlined in the BMC. Consider factors such as expertise in ICT solutions, cybersecurity services, research and engineering capabilities, and access to project funding. 	<p>What areas require improvement or show vulnerabilities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify weaknesses or limitations within IQB's business model, activities, resources, or relationships. Evaluate areas where IQB may face challenges or constraints, such as limited market reach, resource constraints, or technological limitations.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider aspects that may hinder IQB's ability to achieve project's objectives or compete effectively in the market afterwards.
O Opportunities	T Threats
What unique resources or advantages can you leverage? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse external opportunities in the market or industry that IQB can capitalize on. Consider market trends, emerging technologies, regulatory changes, and potential collaborations or partnerships related to SSI and the Identity Management technologies. Identify areas where IQB can expand its market presence, leverage its expertise, or tap into new revenue streams. 	How do others perceive potential challenges or threats to your organization or project? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify external threats or challenges that may impact IQB's business model or operations during the project lifetime. Consider factors such as market dynamics, technological disruptions, and regulatory risks. Evaluate potential obstacles that IQB may encounter in achieving its goals or maintaining its competitive position.

2.5.3 VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

Table 29 : VPC Analysis Ex.Out. #5

Benefits	Description	Wants	Description
Identity Management leveraging the SSI technology	IQB's solution offers the benefit of establishing a secure, trustworthy, and decentralized edge ecosystem within the OASEES framework.	Stakeholders want a solution that enables native device support and integrates Self Sovereign Identity (SSI) for a portable digital identity.	IQB's solution fulfils the need for a new class of identifier that meets all four requirements: persistence, global resolvability, cryptographic verifiability, and decentralization.
Features	Description	Needs	Description
SSI for IoT and edge devices	IQB's solution includes features such as SSI integration, native device	Stakeholders need a solution that provides secure and trustworthy	IQB's solution addresses the need for robust identity management and

	support, decentralized device identity generation, and cryptographic verifiability.	edge ecosystem support while ensuring portable digital identity and decentralization.	secure communication channels in decentralized edge environments.
Experience	Description	Fears	Description
Security and Privacy	Stakeholders will experience enhanced security, privacy, and flexibility in managing their digital identities and edge ecosystem interactions.	Stakeholders may fear the risks associated with centralized identity management, data breaches, and lack of control over their digital identities.	IQB's solution alleviates fears by offering decentralized identity management, cryptographic security, and full control over digital identities.
Ideal Customer	Description	Substitutes	Description
IoT and edge devices	IQB's ideal customer includes organizations and enterprises seeking to deploy edge computing solutions in various industries, such as healthcare, manufacturing, and smart cities.	Potential substitutes for IQB's solution include centralized identity management platforms, traditional cloud-based solutions, and proprietary edge computing frameworks.	IQB's solution offers unique advantages over substitutes by providing decentralized identity management, enhanced security, and compatibility with OASEES standards.

Table 30: VPC Ex. Out. #5

<i>Designed for:</i>				<i>Designed by:</i>				<i>Date:</i>				<i>Version:</i>			
Value Proposition Canvas															
Benefits				Experience				Wants				Fears			

Identity Management leveraging the SSI technology.	Security and Privacy	Stakeholders want a solution that enables native device support and integrates Self Sovereign Identity (SSI) for a portable digital identity.	Stakeholders may fear the risks associated with centralized identity management, data breaches, and lack of control over their digital identities.
Features SSI for IoT and edge devices		Needs Stakeholders need a solution that provides secure and trustworthy edge ecosystem support while ensuring portable digital identity and decentralization.	
Product Identity Management leveraging the SSI technology for IoT and edge devices	Ideal Customer IoT and edge devices	Substitutes Centralized identity management platforms, traditional cloud-based solutions, and proprietary edge computing frameworks.	

2.6 EXPLOITABLE OUTCOME #6 – SCM GROUP

Table 31 : Exploitable Outcome #6

Owner	SCM Group
Contributors	ROBOTNIK - a robotics company, which plays the role of technology provider of the Use Case
Ownership per Implementation	N/A
Protection Measures	N/A

Usage Rights	N/A
Licensing Information	N/A
Notes	N/A

2.6.1 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

This is the BMC analysis on behalf of SCM.

Within the project OASEES, SCM will be able to implement an existing product on its own, by collaborating with projects' partners (more specifically: Robotnik)

Table 32 : BMC Analysis Ex. Out. #6

Key Partners	Role
OASEES partners	Consortium Partners
ROBOTNIK	Technology Provider UC5
Key Activities	Description
Implementation of sanding machinery through cobots and AMRs	The main activity concerns the implementation and the optimization of sanding machinery's process through the help of a collaborative robot and autonomous robots
Key Resources	Description
Sanding machine, wood panels, sanding tools	Tools to be used within the UC
Sanding product manager	Expert who contributes with his expertise to all the issues regarding sanding machinery
Value Propositions	Description
Automation of sanding process	To automate the sanding process through the help of a set of robots, to relieve the human operator from dangerous operations
Customer Relationships	Description
Cooperative alliances with partners, in order to fulfil stakeholder requirements	Becoming the product automated, and collaborating with the partners, SCM aims to increase its customer relationship, by presenting a solution which results as more convenient in terms of productivity, efficiency and human effort
Channels	Description
Sale, export	Firms and factories who need a more performing machinery for the sanding processes
Customer Segments	Description
Industrial	Factories, manufacturing producers and similar
Cost Structure	Description
Products relates	Costs which have to be considered for the effective application of robots on machinery's processes
Operational effort	Product manager and engineers who contribute to the project with their expertise
Revenue Streams	Description

Sale, export

Firms and factories who need a more performing and effective machinery for their sanding processes

Table 33 : BMC Ex.. Out. #6

Business Model Canvas	Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
	OASEES	SCM Group	15.04.2024	1.0
<p><u>Key Partners</u></p> <p>Consortium Partners; Robotnik, an organisation which designs and manufactures autonomous and collaborative robots</p> <p>MOTIVATIONS FOR PARTNERSHIPS:</p> <p>Implementation of product, Automation of</p>	<p><u>Key Activities</u></p> <p>Implementation of sanding machinery through collaborative robots</p> <p>CATEGORIES: Automation, Problem Solving</p>	<p><u>Value Propositions</u></p> <p>Through the automation of the sanding process, it will be possible to optimize the performance of the sanding machine and to relieve the operation of the human resources, which often result as very dangerous</p> <p>CHARACTERISTIC S:</p>	<p><u>Customer Relationships</u></p> <p>Customers will be interested and engaged given that this innovative product will let them have an automated solution which will increase productivity and save human effort</p>	<p><u>Customer Segments</u></p> <p>Products are mainly directed to the industrial sector (factories, manufacturing producers etc.)</p>

<p>operations, Optimization of activities, Reduction of risk</p>	<p><u>Key Resources</u></p> <p>Sanding machine, wood panels, robots, sanding tools</p> <p>Expertise of product manager and engineers</p> <p>TYPES OF RESOURCES: Tools, Machinery, Technical expertise</p>	<p>Implementation, Optimization, Automation, Risk Reduction, Convenience/Usability</p>	<p><u>Channels</u></p> <p>Sale, export</p>	
<p><u>Cost Structure</u></p> <p>Costs are mainly related to the effective effort of product managers and engineers and to the usage and application of operational tools (sanding machine, sanding tools, wood panels, etc.).</p>		<p><u>Revenue Streams</u></p> <p>Sale, export</p>		

2.6.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

Table 34 : SWOT Analysis Ex. Out. #6

S Strengths	W Weaknesses
<p>What are your key competencies and strengths?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Machinery expertise (and expertise regarding tools to be used) - Innovation - Partnership 	<p>What areas require improvement or show vulnerabilities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competitive market
O Opportunities	T Threats

<p>What unique resources or advantages can you leverage?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Industrial excellence - Integration of innovative technologies - Engagement with partners, also within European projects 	<p>How do others perceive potential challenges or threats to your organization or project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competitive industry - Speed of the market
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2.6.3 VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

Table 35 : VPC Analysis Ex.Out. #6

Benefits	Description	Wants	Description
Automation of sanding process	The benefit obtained from the product to be developed within Oasees relates to the automation of an activity (sanding process) which is usually performed by a human operator; this activity is often at high operational risk	Productivity and safety	The main want is related to the increase of productivity (therefore of operational activities within the sanding process) and the increase of safety (therefore relieving the human operator from dangerous situations and high-risk tasks)
Features	Description	Needs	Description
Sanding machine with cobots and AMRs	Sanding machine will be integrated in its operational tasks by a collaborative robot; the “cobot” will perform the activity usually done by the human operator; wood panels will be moved by AMRs (autonomous robots)	Efficiency, safety, productivity	The main customer’ need is probably related in having an innovative product which increases productivity and reduces costs
Experience	Description	Fears	Description
Innovation and efficiency	The main experience related to the final product is related in having an innovative		Main fears are related to the level of excellence of

OASEES D6.2 BUSINESS PLAN

	product, which is efficient and innovative, that reduces costs and increases productivity, also increasing safety of operations	Competition	probable competitors of the sector
Ideal Customer	Description	Substitutes	Description
Seeking for innovation and excellence	Ideal customer is the one who wants to increase productivity with regard of human safety; also, who is really interested in having a unique and innovative industrial product	Companies who engage robotics with the sector of industrial machinery	Substitutes may be related to the level of industrial excellence of competitors

Table 36 : VPC Ex. Out. #6

		<i>Designed for:</i>	<i>Designed by:</i>	<i>Date:</i>	<i>Version:</i>
Value Proposition Canvas		OASEES	SCM Group	15.04.2024	1.0
Benefits	Experience	Wants	Fears		
The benefit obtained from the product to be developed within Oasees is related to the automation of the sanding process. This process is indeed usually performed by a human operator, incurring, in this way, in a high operational risk.	The main experience related to the final product is in having an innovative product, which is efficient and innovative, that reduces costs and increases productivity, also increasing safety of operations	The main want is related to the increase of productivity and the increase of safety	Main fear is related to the speed of the market and to the level of industrial excellence of competitors of the sector		
Features		Needs			

<p>Sanding machine will be integrated in its operational tasks by a collaborative robot, the cobot, which performs in activities usually done by human operators; wood panels will be moved by AMRs (autonomous robots)</p>		<p>The main customer' need is mainly related into having an innovative product in order to increase productivity and reduce costs</p>	
<p>Product</p> <p>Sanding machine integrated with cobots and AMRs</p>	<p>Ideal Customer</p> <p>Ideal customer is who wants to increase productivity with regard of human safety; also, who is really interested in having a unique and innovative industrial product</p>	<p>Substitutes</p> <p>Substitutes may be related to the level of industrial excellence of competitors</p>	

2.7 EXPLOITABLE OUTCOME #7 – SENSO

Table 37 : Exploitable Outcome #7

Owner	Senso Engineering BV
Contributors	Axon
Ownership per Implementation	N/A
Protection Measures	Authorship Industrial Property

Usage Rights	Possible Open-Source derived business model
	Available for partners in the context and duration of the project
Licensing Information	No licensing terms yet. Possibly Open-Source.
Notes	N/A

2.7.1 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Table 38 : BMC Analysis Ex. Out. #7

Key Partners	Role
OASEES Partners	OASEES platform development
Infrachain, Demokritos	DAO
Axon	Quantum computing and integration to our systems
Key Activities	Description
Seismic sensor data collection	Collection and storage of seismic data is part of this activity. Seismic data is a high-frequency, intensive data that require special treatment. How the data will be collected at the edge, what type of data will be transferred to a central computer will be part of this activity.
Earthquake data and signal processing	Establishing scripts and software components for automatically processing the earthquake sensor data.
Hardware / Software Integration for Low-Cost Edge Sensors	Development Use of available low-cost seismic sensors, integration with a Raspberry Pi computer, integration of edge computer and the Night Watch® software with the sensor data at the edge, adaptation and scaling of the Night Watch® software for the edge computer hardware limitations.
Edge communication and system setup	Communication between the sensor and the edge computer, as well as communication between the edge computer and the central computer and/or use groups and client.
Key Resources	Description
Seismic sensor network	A network of seismic sensors, established in Turkey, at various client locations
Earthquake engineer	Experts who can interpret the processed seismic data
Backend software developer	Expert on Django and other relevant components, server systems and automatic data handling
Hardware design and implementation	Person who can implement the software to the smaller capacity edge device
Value Propositions	Description
A more reliable seismic event decision making system	By eliminating the issues related to centralized computer, such as whole system failures and communication problems, the system will be much

	more reliable since it will be running on distributed edge systems.
Faster seismic event decision making system	The computational power will be next to the sensor itself, significantly reducing the latency, which is a key component in the business.
Lower cost and energy consumption seismic network via smart edge devices	Smart edge devices will allow not only fast and reliable, but also lower cost and lower energy consumption systems. The seismic sensors used at the moment cost 4 to 5 times more than the low-cost sensors. Smart edge devices will boost the efficiency of the low-cost sensors, allowing a lower entry-level costs associated with setting up the Night Watch® system to the premises of the customer.
Customer Relationships	Description
Preliminary earthquake assessment and design of a suitable seismic monitoring network	Assessment of the seismicity of the region and the general vulnerability class of the set of buildings of interest, development of a seismic monitoring network according to the expert opinion
Development of operation criteria	Communication with the customer, finding out sensitivities and vulnerabilities, development of operation criteria and the alarm thresholds in case of a seismic event
NightWatch system setup	Setup of the NightWatch seismic monitoring system (sensors, communication via GSM data network, backend server, e-mail and SMS lists for communication, reporting format etc.)
Annual tabletop drills	Tabletop scenario-based earthquake drills with the relevant operational and administrative personnel for better understanding the decision making process and the role of our products
Channels	Description
Operation and Maintenance teams of assets	People responsible with the continuity of the operations, and people who have the tasks of inspection and maintenance
Asset owners	Owners or managers of valuable structural assets
Safety and security management of assets	People responsible with the safety and security of the asset and personnel
Customer Segments	Description
Industrial	Industrial facilities, power plants, refineries, factories
Residential	Large block of flats or clusters of block of flats, or the administrative companies dealing with large block of flats
Infrastructure	Tunnels, bridges, airports
Cost Structure	Description
Personnel (earthquake engineer, backend software developer, hardware developer and integrator)	Experienced personnel and different disciplines, such as software and earthquake engineering fields
Server rental use	Linux servers are rented for deployment and data storage

GSM lines bills	Each client network works with multiple GSM data lines
Hardware costs	Costs for building low-cost sensors
Maintenance costs	Sending over maintenance personnel, direct support in case of malfunctioning or loss of communication with the sensors
Revenue Streams	Description
Annual service agreements and three-monthly payments	Client pays the use of the Night Watch® services. Minimum agreement duration is annual. Most customers opt for 4+1 years agreements, where the 5 th year is free if a 5-year agreement is made. Service fee is charged three-monthly invoices.

Table 39 : BMC Ex. Out. #7

Business Model Canvas	Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
	Entrepreneurs, Earthquake Safety Planners, Business Owners	Senso Engineering	10.04.2024	v1.0

<u>Key Partners</u>	<u>Key Activities</u>	<u>Value Propositions</u>	<u>Customer Relationships</u>	<u>Customer Segments</u>
<p>All OASEES partners are important for developing and helping of deployment of the OASEES platform.</p> <p>Infil and Demokritos are key partners for DAO implementation.</p> <p>Axon is a key partner for testing quantum acceleration in exponential scaling up.</p> <p>MOTIVATIONS FOR PARTNERSHIPS:</p> <p>All partners: Successful implementation of the OASEES platform for Use Case 4 (and all other use cases)</p> <p>Infil & Demokritos: Successful DAO deployment via UC4.</p> <p>Axon: A practical application of quantum acceleration.</p>	<p>Research on tackling specific challenges for deploying UC4 at the edge, over the OASEES platform</p> <p>Production of a new, lighter, more reliable and more efficient version of the existing product</p> <p>Addressing problems of the existing system (NightWatch)</p> <p>CATEGORIES:</p> <p>Research, Production, Problem Solving</p>	<p>A totally new version of NightWatch system will be employed for seismic monitoring o assets. This version will be working at the edge, with a totally new paradigm of distributed computing and data handling.</p> <p>Since the computation will be next to the sensor (source), and due to the demanding nature of the high frequency seismic data, a higher performance will be achieved</p> <p>Reduction of costs via removing many servers from the equation, decreasing the communication with a central computer, shifting to low-cost sensors at the edge, and decreasing person x hours will be possible.</p> <p>With the reduction of costs, the prices will be lowered.</p>	<p>Our customers require an open channel with an expert at Senso because of the type of business (i.e. critical decision making after earthquakes). We need at least one earthquake engineering expert available at any time. This is part of our usual business model and does not bring an additional cost via OASEES.</p> <p>Another important relationship is the annual tabletop drills, where we explain what we do, why we do, and what kind of outputs our product produces, and how they can be used by the customer.</p>	<p>Industrial partners, critical facilities, large asset owners, large residential buildings owners or managers in highly seismic areas</p>

	<p><u>Key Resources</u></p> <p>Use of the existing seismic network of Senso</p> <p>Use of the existing datasets collected by Senso over the years</p> <p>Use of specific expertise and skillset on earthquake engineering and software development intersection</p> <p>TYPES OF RESOURCES: Physical, Intellectual, Human</p>	<p>The system working at the edge will have higher reliability, significantly decreasing the risks at the client side and at our side.</p> <p>The final goal is to provide business continuity to the customers after strong earthquakes.</p> <p>CHARACTERISTIC S: Newness, Performance, Price, Cost Reduction, Risk Reduction</p>	<p><u>Channels</u></p> <p>We maintain regular meeting and communications with the customers.</p> <p>We also have annual tabletop drills where the key personnel of each customer attends and interactively participates. This is an opportunity to make the role of our product, abilities and limitations clear to all parties.</p>	
<p><u>Cost Structure</u></p> <p>Personnel cost</p> <p>Sensor procurement and maintenance costs</p>	<p><u>Revenue Streams</u></p> <p>Customers pay for a product that it will give them business continuity after an earthquake. They pay per annual service contracts. This system works for long, and for all so far.</p> <p>TYPES: Usage fee, Subscription Fees</p> <p>FIXED PRICING: Customer segment dependent, Volume dependent</p>			

2.7.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

Table 40 : SWOT Analysis Ex. Out. #7

S	Strengths	W	Weaknesses
	<p>What are your key competencies and strengths?</p> <p>We have a unique position at the intersection of earthquake engineering, structural engineering and software development, relatively small competition</p>		<p>What areas require improvement or show vulnerabilities?</p> <p>Our value proposition is somehow too technical, while the target persons in customers are usually non-technical. We need to find easier ways of explaining the value of what we are doing.</p>
O	Opportunities	T	Threats
	<p>What unique resources or advantages can you leverage?</p> <p>Even the existing competition is based on classic centralized methods and high-cost sensors. If we can shift to the edge and use low-cost sensors at the same time, we can have a great advantage</p>		<p>How do others perceive potential challenges or threats to your organization or project?</p> <p>Although we do not sell seismic sensors, but we only use them, the sensors companies see us as a threat. Shifting to low-cost sensors may strengthen this perception.</p>

2.7.3 VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

Table 41 : VPC Analysis Ex.Out. #7

Benefits	Description	Wants	Description
Post-earthquake detailed information for easy decision making	Detailed data-driven engineering report with a pre-defined content and format	A reliable system	A monitoring system that can function during severe earthquakes, with energy and communication problems
Continuous monitoring, communication and keeping the earthquake awareness high up	With daily status reports, regular meetings with the relevant personnel, and with the annual tabletop drills	A fast system	A system that can detect the effects of the earthquake fast enough (within a minute following the peak of a large earthquake)

Clear information for the severity of the earthquake at the asset location	Recorded earthquake effects data for post-earthquake insurance and liability assessment	Un interpretable system by non-engineers as well	Outcomes for an easy decision making by a non-technical personnel
Features	Description	Needs	Description
Without the need of human intervention	Automatic reporting in case of an earthquake, independent of the time and day the event happens	How to create an alternative way of communication	In case 4G/LTE/5G collapses during the earthquake, what are the alternative ways to overcome this problem and still inform the customer?
Failure-free	Several proven check and balances to minimize the failure of the monitoring system		
Fast and reliable	Fast thanks to the embedded watch-dog structure, and reliable due to its failure-free nature		
Tailor-made outputs per customer			
Experience	Description	Fears	Description
Seismic monitoring		System not functioning during a major earthquake	
Structural response		Loss of communication during a major earthquake	
		False alarm during an irrelevant event	
Working with high-frequency data (in terms of communication/data transfer and failure-free software development)		Experience in special conditions of seismic monitoring and critical assets	

Ideal Customer	Description	Substitutes	Description
Eurasia Tunnel	A state-of-the-art seismic monitoring system, well maintained monitoring network, knowledgeable personnel, very high level of awareness	Sensor companies also provide a reporting service	Companies producing seismic sensors also provide reporting services. Although what they provide is not the same with our services, they claim it is, and it usually confuses the customer
		Earthquake early warning systems	Early warning is a different method and different technology, and not useful in most cases, but it is more appealing to many customers

Table 42 : VPC Ex. Out. #7

		<i>Designed for:</i>	<i>Designed by:</i>	<i>Date:</i>	<i>Version:</i>
Value Proposition Canvas		Critical Facility Owners or Managers	Senso Engineering	10.04.2024	v1.0
Benefits NightWatch® is a post-earthquake detailed information for easy decision making. If detects an earthquake, it provides a detailed data-driven engineering report with a pre-defined content and format. With the continuous monitoring, communication and	Experience Senso has experience in seismic monitoring and response of structures to severe earthquakes. Furthermore, the company also has experience in working with high-frequency data (in terms of communication/dat	Wants Customers need a reliable earthquake decision support system. This can be achieved by creating a system that can function during severe earthquakes, with energy and communication problems. The system should also be reasonably fast since the time matter	Fears Major fears are: System not functioning during a major earthquake Loss of communication during a major earthquake False alarm during an irrelevant event Experience in special conditions of seismic		

<p>keeping the earthquake awareness high up, it helps customers to better prepare for an earthquake. It provides clear information for the severity of the earthquake at the asset location.</p>	<p>a transfer and failure-free software development)</p>	<p>following a large earthquake situation.</p> <p>The outputs of the decision support system should be easily interpretable by non-technical personnel</p>	<p>monitoring and critical assets</p>
<p>Features</p> <p>Nightwatch works without human intervention, it is designed to be failure-free, fast and reliable. It can produce tailor-made post-earthquake outputs per customer.</p>		<p>Needs</p> <p>We need to create alternative communication ways or alternative reporting channels. In case 4G/LTE/5G collapses during the earthquake, what are the alternative ways to overcome this problem and still inform the customer?</p>	
<p>Product</p> <p>NightWatch seismic monitoring and decision support system</p>	<p>Ideal Customer</p> <p>Eurasia Tunnel</p> <p>A state-of-the-art seismic monitoring system, well maintained monitoring network, knowledgeable personnel, very high level of awareness</p>		<p>Substitutes</p> <p>Companies producing seismic sensors also provide reporting services. Although what they provide is not the same with our services, they claim it is, and it usually confuses the customer</p> <p>Companies with early warning systems also try to substitute our services. However, earthquake early warning is a different method and different technology, and not useful in most cases, but it is more appealing to many customers.</p>

2.8 EXPLOITABLE OUTCOME #8 - FOKUS

Table 43 : Exploitable Outcome #8

Owner	FOKUS
Contributors	NKUA NCSR
Ownership per Implementation	NCSR: Drone Route Optimization
Protection Measures	No protection measures, since Qrisp is open-source.
Usage Rights	Qrisp is open-source and usable for everyone under the EPL 2.0 license.
Licensing Information	Eclipse Public License 2.0 (EPL 2.0)
Notes	N/A

2.8.1 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Table 44 : BMC Analysis Ex. Out. #8

Key Partners	Role
OASEES Partners	OASEES Platform
Demokritos	User
Tecnalia	Data Collection
Key Activities	Description
Build algorithm modules	Implement algorithms to be utilized for the optimization problems OASEES tries to tackle
Example Use cases	Utilize algorithms in Qrisp to potentially speed up the optimization calculations within the use cases
Building a Qrisp Community	Bring together a community of experts to contribute to Qrisp through the Eclipse Foundation. Reaching a critical mass of involved people is critical to reach the critical, self-sustaining mass of users
Key Resources	Description
Qrisp Quantum Devkit	Following the Open-Source strategy of OASEES the already existing open-source framework Eclipse Qrisp is chosen to be further developed in OASEES, such that it can be applied in several use cases.
Qrisp QAOA module	Quantum Approximate Optimisation Algorithm, or QAOA for short, is a hybrid quantum-classical variational algorithm designed for solving combinatorial optimization problems.

Qrisp module benchmarking	The benchmarking module provides detailed analysis of using various quantum computing hardware using the well-known benchmarking metrics.
Drone Fleet route optimization	Utilizing the implementations of quantum algorithms in Qrisp we obtain an optimized route for the Drone Fleet use-case.
Qrisp Backtracking module	The Quantum Backtracking Algorithm proposed by Ashley Montanaro is based on the use of a quantum walk algorithm to search in the backtracking tree.
Quantum Debugging Framework	The Quantum Debugging framework allows the user to obtain an insight into the sophisticated QuantumVariable abstraction in Qrisp. Utilizing these tools makes implementing algorithms easier to comprehend.
Quantum DevOps	Quantum DevOps allows a streamlined workflow to select the best matching (cloud) QC instance and having it integrated directly with the processes of development, testing and finally the operations of quantum based algorithms and systems.
Value Propositions	Description
Use quantum algorithms with little pre-knowledge	
Open Science	Open Science is supported by developing Qrisp as open development package on GitHub. This way the development can be followed by everyone and everyone can contribute in the development.
Easy scaling of solutions	
Assess potential of quantum technologies for industry purposes	It's easier to get an idea of the potential quantum computing can have on a company's business
Customer Relationships	Description
Forming cooperative alliances with consortium partners	Working together on use case with Demokritos; Collaborative benchmarking of different Quantum SDKs with QAOA algorithm with Tecnalía
Open-Source and Open Development	Via Eclipse Foundation governance processes
Forming cooperative alliances with research institutions and universities	Qrisp Community, Slack, GitHub, ...
Channels	Description
Slack	The central point usersusersng about the next steps and bugfixes.
Qrisp Community	A self-sustaining community that helps contribute to Qrisp
Eclipse Qrisp GitHub repository	Main repository where contributions can be performed
Fairs and conferences	e.g Hannover Messe
Customer Segments	Description
Universities	Using Qrisp in a course

OASEES D6.2 BUSINESS PLAN

Industry/ public agencies	Using implemented Qrisp modules
Logistic IT companies	Using implemented Qrisp optimization modules
IT industry	Using implemented Qrisp cryptography modules
Finance industry	Using implemented Qrisp optimization modules
Cost Structure	Description
Personal costs	Salaries, travel to conferences, etc.
Revenue Streams	Description
Membership fee	Just for Qrisp Community
Free	Qrisp itself is open-source and will always be
Teachings	

Table 45 : BMC Ex. Out. #8

Business Model Canvas	Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
	Software Developers	FOKUS	19.04.2024	1.0
<p><u>Key Partners</u></p> <p>Research centers</p> <p>MOTIVATIONS FOR PARTNERSHIPS: Optimization and economy, Reduction of risk and uncertainty, Acquisition of particular resources and activities.</p>	<p><u>Key Activities</u></p> <p>We are implementing and utilizing algorithms in Qrisp to potentially speed up the optimization calculations within the OASEES use cases.</p> <p>Additionally, we are working in building a Qrisp Community to bring together experts to contribute to Qrisp.</p>	<p><u>Value Propositions</u></p> <p>We are creating value for all classical programmers that are looking to tackle programming quantum algorithms. Of course, there is also value for existing quantum programmes through sophisticated abstraction Qrisp introduces, which make quantum algorithm development and</p>	<p><u>Customer Relationships</u></p> <p>Our customers expect responsiveness when it comes to helping them use our quantum SDK, as well as when it comes to fixing bugs when they are observed.</p> <p>This is integrated through the slack communication channel, as well as Qrisp Community.</p> <p>The costs are the cost of personnel.</p>	<p><u>Customer Segments</u></p> <p>We are creating value for all classical programmers that are looking to tackle programming quantum algorithms. Of course, there is also value for existing quantum programmes through sophisticated abstraction Qrisp introduces.</p> <p>We would like to reach a critical mass of users in order for the project to become self-sustaining with other programmers contributing to it.</p>

	<p><u>Key Resources</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Qrisp Quantum DevKit - Qrisp Algorithmic Modules - Quantum DevOps - Developers enhancing the Qrisp Quantum SDK <p>TYPES OF RESOURCES: Intellectual property made public via an open-source approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - human resources: developers working on Qrisp have a huge knowledge in quantum computing programming. 	<p>implementation more efficient.</p> <p>Our value is creating the first functional high-level quantum programming framework, which doesn't approach algorithm design by direct manipulation of qubits. Instead the introduced abstractions provide a familiar feel akin to classical programming approaches.</p>	<p><u>Channels</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slack Qrisp Community Eclipse Qrisp GitHub Repository Fairs and conferences 	
<p><u>Cost Structure</u></p> <p>The most important costs are the personal costs of the developers working on further developing Qrisp, alongside with travel costs for conferences etc.</p>	<p><u>Revenue Streams</u></p> <p>Qrisp itself is an open-source software under the Eclipse Foundation and as such will stay open and free of charge for everyone to use.</p> <p>There will however be a Qrisp Community, where companies, research intitutes can participate and will get additional information and activities and knowledge around Qrisp.</p> <p>The pricing will depend on the size of the company and what kind of entity applies for a membership. In this sense it will be an annual fixed membership fee.</p>			

2.8.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

Table 46 : SWOT Analysis Ex. Out. #8

S	Strengths	W	Weaknesses
	What are your key competencies and strengths? Improve constructing quantum programs Experience in implementing complex algorithms. Cutting edge research in deep tech technology		What areas require improvement or show vulnerabilities? Few quantum computers easily accessible Hard to reach critical mass to develop open-source software after public funding
O	Opportunities	T	Threats
	What unique resources or advantages can you leverage? Only Quantum SDK that uses Variables and Functions instead if qubits and gates Possible advantages that quantum algorithms offer over classical algorithms		How do others perceive potential challenges or threats to your organization or project? Quantum Computers won't become "good enough" to yield advantage in the next 10 or more years. Other, better Quantum SDK emerges

2.8.3 VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

Table 47: VPC Analysis Ex.Out. #8

Benefits	Description	Wants	Description
High-level quantum programming SDK	A high-level quantum programming SDK with many features and programming abstractions not found in other quantum SDK's, which allow many benefits (as seen in fields below).	Easy access to quantum computing hardware	Customers would like to use their existing access to quantum hardware from within the SDK. Many
Technological sovereignty	Manufacturer independence enables variability and selection of the most suitable provider at all	Industry-specific services based on quantum algorithms	Users want modules for specific use cases which they can easily use and adapt to their problems. This involves fast

	times enables quality assurance		prototyping and easy access to hardware is suited best for their problem.
Features	Description	Needs	Description
Variables and functions instead of qubits and gates	Using programming abstractions like variables instead of qubits helps structuring the code immensely. Using these concepts allows users to start thinking in a quantum way that resembles a programmer, instead of someone chaining together unitary matrices.	Industry-scale software	Existing software solutions do not meet industry standards in terms of version management. There are to often breaking changes. Something we are changing with Qrisp.
Modularity	Modularity is a property that groups the code into separate organizational units, which interact less. It allows a team of programmers to work on different parts of the code without having to frequently reach agreements. This results in separate domain experts working together.	Structured testing of quantum code	Validation of the solutions, testing in other frameworks is very complicated and tedious.
Platform Independence	Advantage of running code on a variety of backends. Qrisp supports a variety of circuit conversion functions, but the true platform independence comes from its architecture: because of its dynamic qubit management, the implementation of virtually any elementary function can be replaced such that the same code compiles to an entirely different circuit.	Avoid vendor lock-in	High risk due to manufacturer dependency, both in terms of technical restrictions and economic factors. This has to be avoided by choosing the right software framework.
Experience	Description	Fears	Description

<p>Basic programming skills</p>	<p>The customer should possess the basics of programming in Python. All features of the Qrisp quantum computing SDK are intuitively described in easy-to-follow interactive tutorials.</p>	<p>Reaching critical mass of users</p>	<p>Dissemination of Qrisp would only be successful when a critical mass of users is reached resulting in a self-sustaining ecosystem. Once that is reached, the Qrisp SDK will be developed by other contributors under the scope of the democratic nature of the Eclipse Foundation.</p>
<p>Easy access</p>	<p>All features of the Qrisp quantum computing SDK are intuitively described in easy-to-follow interactive tutorials.</p>	<p>Competitors</p>	<p>Other companies could work on a framework with a similar structure like Qrisp and more manpower and basically copy it. But this is not happening right now.</p>
<p>Ideal Customer</p>	<p>Description</p>	<p>Substitutes</p>	<p>Description</p>
<p>Programmer/Software Developer</p>	<p>Classical programmers tend to be aversive when it comes to entering the field of quantum computing and quantum information science because it is based on quantum mechanics. To develop quantum algorithms, one first has to go through the basic theory allowing that. Qrisp's high-level approach allows these same classical programmers to instead feel more familiar with its syntax, which reminds that of classical code. For example, the abstractions in Qrisp allow for creating QuantumVariables, QuantumFloats, etc., similarly to how one would create Variables, Floats, etc. In classical programming.</p>	<p>Other Python Quantum SDKs</p>	<p>Already available frameworks, which don't provide the same experience as Qrisp are, e.g. PennyLane, Qiskit</p>

<p>Quantum Algorithm designer</p>	<p>Abstractions allowing variables and functions instead of direct qubit and gate manipulations offers immense advantage in implementing complex algorithms. This is showcased with the Quantum Backtracking module, which implementation is not possible on other frameworks.</p>	<p>Other Quantum Programming Languages</p> <p>Few dedicated quantum programming languages are already available, e.g. Q#, SilQ, which can be used for programming quantum computers although they don't provide the same experience as Qrisp.</p>
<p>R&D Unit leader</p>	<p>Using the Qrisp quantum SDK allows R&D units an easier transition into the field of quantum computation. It allows being active in this field which shows great promise on topics like optimization, material simulations, etc.</p>	

2.9 EXPLOITABLE OUTCOME #9 - INFILI

Table 49 : Exploitable Outcome #9

<p>Owner</p>	<p>Infil as main owner of the anomaly-detection and vulnerability-detection algorithms will develop, test and implement the AI models into the OASEES framework.</p>
<p>Contributors</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Ownership per Implementation</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Protection Measures</p>	<p>Under BSD license</p>
<p>Usage Rights</p>	<p>The AI algorithms will be provided as a service within the OASEES stack. Free usage rights of the consortium partners in collaboration with Infil.</p>
<p>Licensing Information</p>	<p>Open-source license, such as BSD license.</p>
<p>Notes</p>	<p>N/A</p>

2.9.1 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Table 50 : BMC Analysis Ex. Out. #9

Key Partners	Role
Partners of the Consortium	Infilu will develop machine-learning based anomaly and vulnerability-detection algorithms and provide security analytics for the edge device network traffic and the smart contracts within OASEES.
Key Activities	Description
Research and development in deep learning and cybersecurity, implementation of the modules in the OASEES framework	Design, development and implementation of security-related modules in the OASEES framework, both for network and smart-contract security.
Key Resources	Description
Expertise in cybersecurity and AI technologies, open-source datasets, security analytics tools developed in previous projects	Based on the expertise and the resources available in our company, the security modules for OASEES can be developed and implemented.
Value Propositions	Description
Providing smart and adaptable multi-modal security analytics based on deep-learning algorithms	Infilu offers cutting-edge machine-learning algorithms applied in the realm of (cyber-)security and anomaly detection. OASEES edge devices connected within the OASEES network will be analysed for anomalous network behaviour, such that security at the edge is provided.
Providing smart and adaptable multi-modal smart-contract vulnerability scans based on deep-learning algorithms	In particular, multi-modal deep-learning-based smart-contract vulnerability detection will enhance the trustworthiness and security of OASEES smart contracts.
Customer Relationships	Description
Partnerships with consortium partners, stakeholders, and end users of the OASEES framework	Collaboration with consortium partners (e.g. LIST on smart contracts) and communication with stakeholders and UC providers/end users
Channels	Description
Project meetings, workshops, conferences, publications, OASEES communication channels	Dissemination in various channels of the project and beyond.
Customer Segments	Description
Consortium partners, stakeholders in AI-assisted cybersecurity, blockchain and DAO developers, smart contract providers	Partners and stakeholders interested in adaptable, cutting-edge cybersecurity and smart contract security
Cost Structure	Description
Personnel cost, R&D and infrastructure cost	Allocate resources for R&D, personnel and minor infrastructure costs, budget within OASEES project
Revenue Streams	Description
European project funding, potential revenue from commercialisation of developed modules	Beyond the project funding by the European Union, potential revenue can be generated upon the commercialisation of the solution beyond the project scope

Table 51 : BMC Ex. Out. #9

Business Model Canvas	Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
<p><u>Key Partners</u></p> <p>Partners of the Consortium</p> <p>MOTIVATIONS FOR PARTNERSHIPS: Optimization and economy, Reduction of risk and uncertainty, Acquisition of particular resources and activities.</p>	<p><u>Key Activities</u></p> <p>Research, design, development and implementation of security-related modules in the OASEES framework, both for network and smart-contract security</p> <p>CATEGORIES: Development, implementation</p> <p><u>Key Resources</u></p> <p>Expertise in cybersecurity and AI technologies, open-source datasets, security analytics tools developed in previous projects</p> <p>TYPES OF RESOURCES: Physical, Intellectual, Human, Financial</p>	<p><u>Value Propositions</u></p> <p>Providing smart and adaptable multi-modal security analytics based on deep-learning algorithms</p> <p>Providing smart and adaptable multi-modal smart-contract vulnerability scans based on deep-learning algorithms</p> <p>CHARACTERISTICS: Newness, Performance, Customization, Design, Risk Reduction, Security, Usability</p>	<p><u>Customer Relationships</u></p> <p>Partnerships with consortium partners, stakeholders, and end users of the OASEES framework</p> <p><u>Channels</u></p> <p>Project meetings, workshops, conferences, publications, OASEES communication channels</p>	<p><u>Customer Segments</u></p> <p>Consortium partners, stakeholders in AI-assisted cybersecurity, blockchain and DAO developers, smart contract providers</p>
	OASEES project	Infil Technologies S.A.	27/03/2024	1.0

<p><u>Cost Structure</u> Personnel cost, R&D and infrastructure cost IS YOUR BUSINESS MORE: Value Driven (focused on value creation, premium value proposition). SAMPLE CHARACTERISTICS: Fixed Costs (salaries, rents, utilities)</p>	<p><u>Revenue Streams</u> For what value are our customers really willing to pay? For what do they currently pay? How are they currently paying? How would they prefer to pay? How much does each Revenue Stream contribute to overall revenues? TYPES: Asset sale, Subscription Fees, FIXED PRICING: List Price, Product feature dependent, Functionality dependent</p>
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2.9.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

Table 52 : SWOT Analysis Ex. Out. #9

S	Strengths	W	Weaknesses
	ICT services, software engineering Expertise in artificial intelligence (machine and deep learning, AI systems) and, particularly, in anomaly detection Cybersecurity, security analytics Research and development Strong experience in European project funding		Number of annotated smart contracts is rather small Dependence on open-source smart contracts for AI-model training
O	Opportunities	T	Threats
	Increase and deepen knowledge and expertise in smart-contract and DAO vulnerability detection Develop service applicable to various use cases containing smart contracts in different fields		Rule-based smart-contract assessments might not be conclusive enough to provide ground truth for AI algorithms. In that case an alternative solution, possibly relying on statistical arguments, is needed.

2.10 EXPLOITABLE OUTCOMES #10 - CAPGEMINI

Table 55 : Exploitable Outcome #10

Owner	Capgemini – In charge to lead the development and integration of the Proof of Concept 6: Smart Swarm Energy harvesting and Predictive Maintenance Wind turbines within OASEES platform.
Contributors	Tecnia: Data sovereignty, Data Product orientation and PoC 6 KPIs validation. Infrachain & NCSR: Marketplace, DAO and Smart contracts development and deployment. NKUA: Algorithms of machine learning and federated learning alignment and orientation.
Ownership per Implementation	Tecnia: Data sovereignty Infrachain & NCSR: Wind Farm DAO, Smart Contracts and DAO
Protection Measures	Patent “Sistema y procedimiento de detección de irregularidades en las palas de un aerogenerador” - ES-2943569_A1 Signed NDAs with wind farm owners (Wind turbine acoustic and data) Source algorithms codes
Usage Rights	Algorithms (Acoustic optimization algorithms, Classifier and predictive anomalies algorithms)
Licensing Information	Algorithms (Acoustic optimization algorithms, Classifier and predictive anomalies algorithms) Datasets (blade acoustic, environmental parameters, wind turbine data)
Notes	NA

2.10.1 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Table 56 : BMC Analysis Ex. Out. #10

OASEES Partners	OASEES platform development
Infrachain, NCSR	DAO
Tecnia	Data sovereignty, Data Product, Pilot KPIs
NKUA	ML/FL features
Capgemini	PoC 6 development and integration
Key Activities	Description
BAMS swarm	Development of swarm acoustic monitoring system (IoT Devices) in charge to acquire wind turbine acoustic data
Classifier and Predictive Algorithms – Aggregated Algorithms	Development and adaptation of algorithms in charge to classify and predict the anomalies presented in a wind

	turbine blade allowing the collaboration between them through collaborative learning.
Technical Reports, LCOE optimization & dynamic maintenance plan	Elaboration of technical reports according to the algorithms output to be able to show relevant technical-economical indicators such as LCOE, blade health status and anomalies detected which allow to feed the maintenance plan and elaborate a dynamic one according to the anomaly's detection.
Data anonymization	Elaborate and implement a process to anonymize the raw data acquired from wind turbines.
Key Resources	Description
Expertise in acoustics	Acoustics analysis.
Expertise in Data + SW AI/ML algorithms	Advance algorithms for identification and prediction of anomalies using artificial intelligence and neural networks.
Expertise in Wind Turbines	Technical, failures/anomalies, maintenance, and financial wind turbine knowledge.
Value Propositions	Description
Value delivered to customers	Cost reduction, risk reduction, performance, blade status.
Customer's problems are we helping to solve?	Predict failures in wind turbine blades using non-intrusive devices. Reducing maintenance cost and increasing availability of the wind turbine Swarm IoT BAMS Devices Trained algorithms to classify and predict blade failures/anomalies applying collaborative learning methods.
Bundles of products and services are offering?	Dynamic Maintenance Plan according to blade status input. Technical reports with technical and economical relevant indicators, such as blade health status, LCOE (Levelized Cost of Energy)
Satisfaction needs	Reducing uncertainty of blade failures and avoiding unexpected wind turbine stops. Increasing availability of the wind turbine. Optimizing the integrity of the blade. Reducing maintenance cost of the blade
Customer Relationships	Description
What type of relationship does each of our Customer Segments expect us to establish and maintain with them?	Self and periodically assistance
How are they integrated with the rest of our business model?	Through transversal profiles
Partnerships with consortium partners	Collaboration with OASEES partners
Channels	Description
Through which Channel do our Customer Segments want to be reached?	Meetings, portfolio dissemination events, presential demos. Commercial meetings with stakeholders. Content dissemination using social networks.

How are we will reach them?	Meetings, portfolio dissemination events, demos. Commercial meetings with stakeholders, Presential demos OASEES consortium partners collaboration Technical Publications
Which ones are most cost-efficient?	Demos, it has a “wow” component which works like a hook.
Customer Segments	Description
OEMs (Original Equipment Manufacturer)	Siemens Gamesa Vestas General Electric
Companies dedicated to the exploitation of wind and solar energy	Siemens Gamesa Finerge EDP-R Iberdrola Renewables
Companies dedicated to the generation and distribution of electrical energy	Red Eléctrica, RETIT – Wind/PV hybrid systems, power supply for telecommunications equipment Iberdrola Distribution Nedgia
Multi-energy companies	REPSOL CEPSA ENGIE TOTAL Ibertrola Enel Endesa
Cost Structure	Description
Most important costs inherent	Fixed cost (labour cost) Rents (workplaces and IT material) Demonstrator/Equipment
Key Resources	Fixed cost of the team (acoustic engineer, SW engineers, data/AI engineer, project manager)
Key Activities	Presential Dissemination events.
Revenue Streams	Description
Value are our customers willing to pay?	Marketplace algorithm acquisition, subscription fees and usage fees, data acquisition
What do they currently pay?	Trained algorithms (rent or acquisition), anonymized data, technical reports, dynamic maintenance plan (wind turbines), blockchain fees.
How would they prefer to pay?	Bank transfer, wind turbine information, data information, maintenance plan.
How much does each Revenue Stream contribute to overall revenues?	In a 100% of the overall revenue

2.10.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

Table 57 : SWOT Analysis Ex. Out. #10

S	Strengths	W	Weaknesses
	<p>Innovative solution to detect wind turbine blades anomalies which can considerably reduce the O&M cost using non-intrusive swarm IoT devices.</p> <p>Classifier and predictive algorithms enhanced with collaborative learning.</p>		<p>Signal quality of the acoustic data.</p> <p>Accuracy and confidence of the algorithms.</p> <p>Collaborative learning complexity.</p> <p>Massive data management.</p>
O	Opportunities	T	Threats
	<p>Introduce a new and innovative method to detect anomalies in wind turbine blades using collaborative learning.</p> <p>Flexible and dynamics maintenance plans.</p> <p>Create a massive dataset of acoustic wind turbine blades for it anonymize usage.</p> <p>Privacy and data protection between stakeholders (wind farm owners – maintenance companies)</p>		<p>Loss of interest in the technology by the OEMs, wind farm owners and maintenance companies.</p> <p>Cybersecurity: sensitive information could be stolen.</p> <p>The IoT device could be stolen, which could lead to a security breach.</p>

2.10.3 VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

Table 58 : VPC Analysis Ex. Out. #11

Benefits	Description	Wants	Description
	<p>This data service adds value by improving turbine performance, offering non-intrusive monitoring, enabling proactive analysis and detection, ensuring algorithm reliability, evaluating maintenance cost impact, and providing anonymized data for further analysis and development.</p> <p>These advantages collectively contribute to a more efficient and cost-effective management of wind turbine operations.</p>		<p>Cost reduction and reliable systems</p> <p>Improve Operational and Maintenance Expenditure elaborating dynamic maintenance plans and introducing new and innovative alternatives to diagnose blade status.</p>

Features	Description	Needs	Description
Classifier and predictive algorithms for wind turbines anomalies	<p>Signal Processing Methods: identifying relevant features in the sound patterns failures associated with turbine performance and potential.</p> <p>Neural Networks Trained by Collaborative Learning Algorithms: Neural networks, a type of artificial intelligence, will be employed to recognize complex patterns in the acoustic data.</p>	Data quality, uncertainty reduction and cost efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of availability, quality and veracity of the raw acoustic blade data. - Expensive blade failure detection methods. - Wind turbine shutdown for blade inspection.
Experience	Description	Fears	Description
Unique and innovative solution	<p>The combination of pioneering technologies makes BAMS a differential and innovative factor in the market, highlighting the ability to integrate multiple technologies for identification and prediction of failures through non-intrusive devices, improving its results through collaborative learning and maintaining its immutability thanks to the blockchain, in addition to allowing the creation of a market that contributes to the economy and self-sustainability of the ecosystem, without leaving behind the sovereignty of the data.</p>	Technical failure	<p>The main fears are those related to technical failure, in which the system integration and system performance is not able to achieve and meet the target KPIs.</p>
Ideal Customer	Description	Substitutes	Description
	<p>The ideal customer will be the who which are seeking to improve their maintenance systems in wind turbine and are very interested to try innovative</p>	Companies in charge to develop product in charge	<p>Similar technologies which allow to identify the anomalies of the wind blade turbines with more</p>

Next-generation technology stakeholders	solutions which can considerably reduce O&M expenditure and improve their incomes using cutting-edge technology.	to identify anomalies in wind turbine blades	accuracy being non-intrusive.
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2.11 EXPLOITABLE OUTCOME #11 - TECNALIA

Tecnia exploits its assets through Tecnia Ventures. The BMC will be done in collaboration with them once the outcome of the project is mature enough to be consider an exploitation asset according to their criteria.

Table 59 : Exploitable Outcome #11

Owner	TECNALIA
Contributors	FOKUS
Ownership per Implementation	BlockChain Based Broker, Quantum annealing-based algorithm for routing problems nad Quantum DevOps
Protection Measures	Authorship Industrial Property Possible Open-Source derived business models
Usage Rights	Available for partners in the context and duration of the project.
Licensing Information	EUPL
Notes	<p>Tecnia mission is to transform technological research into prosperity. We are agents of transformation of companies and society for their adaptation to the challenges of a changing future.</p> <p>Tecnia will exploit the results from OASEES within the Public Authorities and Private sector to foster the digital transformation of both sectors.</p> <p>Tecnia will also use its participated subsidiary Tecnia Ventures to exploit any result from OASEES that could be further industrialized to become a commercial asset. The current potential assets that could become part of its product portfolio are the Data Product onboarding in Gaia—X as well as the Blockchain Based Broker.</p> <p>Tecnia is keen on collaborating to fully utilize the OASEES DAO, encompassing all the developed components.</p>

2.11.1 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Table 60 : BMC Analysis Ex. Out. #11

Key Partners	Role
OASEES Partners	OASEES platform development
Infrachain, Demokritos	DAO
Key Activities	Description
Data logging and monitorisation	Logging OASEES platform DAO activity initialization and finalisation in a blockchain-based ledger providing decentralization to logs.
Key Resources	Description
Logging broker	The decentralised ledger and the connection interface to interact with OASEES modules (DAO).
Value Propositions	Description
Trustworthy interactions between devices in federated data spaces.	Provide an alternative to centralised logging systems.
Customer Relationships	Description
Collaborative partnerships with consortium partners, stakeholders, and end-users of the use cases	Establishing strong relationships through communication, collaboration, and continuous engagement to ensure alignment with project goals and meet the needs of stakeholders.
Channels	Description
Utilizing project meetings, workshops, conferences, online collaboration platforms, and dedicated communication channels for project coordination.	Employing diverse channels to facilitate efficient communication, collaboration, and distribution of project activities, progress, and outcomes
Asset owners	Description
Safety and security management of assets	Owners or managers of valuable structural assets People responsible with the safety and security of the asset and personnel
Customer Segments	Description
Collaborative partners, end-users, and stakeholders within the domains of data spaces.	Everyone focusing a data space could embrace this need.
Cost Structure	Description
Personnel (R&D cost, personnel expenses)	Assigning resources and budget for research, development, testing, validation, project management, and collaborative endeavors within the framework of the OASEES project.
Infrastructure costs	Infrastructure needed to run the solution will depend on the final deployment design process.
Revenue Streams	Description
Project funding from the European Union, regional contractors, and private investments	Clients may have interest to try the solution in the context of OASEES.

2.11.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

Table 61 : SWOT Analysis Ex. Out. #11

S	Strengths	W	Weaknesses
	<p>What are your key competencies and strengths?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decentralization allows trust to be real, deleting central powerful actors. Easy to solve conflicts due to data mismatch and synchronization between contracting partners or between exchanging partners. 		<p>What areas require improvement or show vulnerabilities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The designs are not finished due to the complexity of the overall system and there's no single point of view over the needs of this kind of components in the community and existing associations.
O	Opportunities	T	Threats
	<p>What unique resources or advantages can you leverage?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Platforms oriented to data spaces are enjoying great potential for the development of new technologies associated with communication within these collaborative systems. 		<p>How do others perceive potential challenges or threats to your organization or project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Due to the novelty of the current designs, the orientation from institutions can change, forcing the project to adapt to new visions. Although the logging needs are not new, the market can avoid the usage of decentralized systems.

2.11.3 VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

Table 62 : VPC Analysis Ex. Out. #11

Benefits	Description	Wants	Description
	<p>Logging registration and monitorisation based on decentralised schemas</p>		<p>The solution offers the benefit of establishing a transparent, trustworthy, and decentralized log registering service for data exchanges and occupancy negotiation.</p>
			<p>Stakeholders want a solution that enables transparency on suspicions of misconduct.</p>
			<p>The solution provides an uninvolved party to register information that could be used in case of conflict between two participants.</p>
Features	Description	Needs	Description
	<p>Logging for DAO interactions</p>		<p>The solution includes features such as logging and integration to data exchange actions from</p>
			<p>transparent and trustworthy demonstration of actions.</p>
			<p>Stakeholders need a solution that provides transparent and trustworthy</p>

	devices and their occupancy with transparency and trusted by third parties that need to supervise them.		communications to demonstrate the correctness of their actions.
Experience	Description	Fears	Description
Enhanced trust	Stakeholders will experience enhanced trust and transparency in managing their digital logs at ecosystem interactions.	Who oversees decentralising the service if there's no owner.	As every decentralised solution, there's a previous work selecting, locating, and contacting the consortium maintaining the service, if it's not intended to be openly maintained by a community.
Ideal Customer	Description	Substitutes	Description
Decentralised platforms and data spaces	The ideal customer in this case could be anyone integrating a platform with logging needs.	Centralised logging services.	A decentralised logging service substitutes classic centralised logging service that are more prone to fail and intentioned modifications, leading to trust losing.

2.12 EXPLOITABLE OUTCOME #12 - ROBOTNIK

Table 63 : Exploitable Outcome #11

Owner	Robotnik Automation S.L. Developer and integrator of PoC 5.
Contributors	SCM and FOKUS – PoC partners
Ownership per Implementation	Infrachain and NCSR – Marketplace, DAO and Smart contracts Other partners – OASEES ecosystem
Protection Measures	N/A
Usage Rights	N/A

Licensing Information	N/A
Notes	N/A

2.12.1 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

In this Business Model Canvas Analysis by Robotnik, we outline our strategy to enhance the RB-THERON, an autonomous mobile robot, through collaboration with all the OASEES Consortium, especially SCM and FOKUS within the project's Use Case 5. SCM's sector expertise is crucial to improving RB-THERON's industrial integration and communication with the robotic arm, advancing our product within the OASEES ecosystem.

Table 64 : BMC Analysis Ex. Out. #12

Key Partners	Role
SCM and FOKUS	Use Case partners
Infrachain and Demokritos	DAO
Other OASEES partners	OASEES platform
Key Activities	Description
Automation of sanding process	Automatic sanding and transport of wooden parts with a mobile robot and a robotic arm, in a safe and collaborative way
Hardware development and software integration	Design and implement the Use Case solution within the OASEES ecosystem
Data analytics	Analyse process data to provide customers with statistical insights
Key Resources	Description
Sanding solution (mobile robot + arm + sanding tool), Wood panels	Solution to be used within the Use Case
Sanding product manager	Expert who contributes with his expertise to all the issues regarding sanding machinery
Value Propositions	Description
Automation of sanding process	To automate the sanding process through the help of a set of robots, to relieve the human operator from dangerous operations
Customer Relationships	Description

Cooperative alliances with partners	Robotnik aims to increase its customer relationship by presenting a more productive, efficient and convenient in terms of human effort solution
Channels	Description
Direct sales	Direct sales to manufacturing and industrial companies
Online platforms	Online platforms for industrial automation solutions
Partner networks	Partner networks including SCM for distribution
Industry trade shows	Industry trade shows and events for demonstrations
Webinars and online tutorials	Webinars and online tutorials for engagement and education
Customer Segments	Description
Industrial and research	Manufacturing companies, industrial facilities, and research institutions seeking automation solutions
Cost Structure	Description
Research and development	For continuous product improvement
Production and manufacturing costs	Including materials for the robots
Partnership and collaboration fees	Particularly with SCM and other entities
Marketing and sales expenses	including trade shows, online platforms, and advertising
Operational costs	Such as logistics, staff salaries, and facility overheads
Revenue Streams	Description
Direct sales	Sales of the autonomous solution to industrial clients
Service and maintenance	Service and maintenance contracts for ongoing support
Licensing fees	For proprietary software used in the integration

Table 65 : BMC Ex. Out. #12

Business Model Canvas	Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
	Industrial and research sectors	The OASEES ecosystem developers,	09/04/2024	1

	seeking automation solutions.	with specific mention of Robotnik.		
<u>Key Partners</u>	<u>Key Activities</u>	<u>Value Propositions</u>	<u>Customer Relationships</u>	<u>Customer Segments</u>
<p>SCM and FOKUS as Use Case partners. Infrachain and Demokritos in the DAO.</p> <p>Other OASEES partners contribute to the ecosystem.</p> <p>Motivations for Partnerships: Economy, acquisition of resources.</p>	<p>Automation of the sanding process.</p> <p>Hardware development and software integration within the OASEES ecosystem.</p> <p>Data analytics for statistical insights.</p> <p>Categories: Production, problem solving.</p> <p><u>Key Resources</u></p> <p>Sanding solution including mobile robot, arm, and sanding tool.</p> <p>Wood panels for the use case.</p> <p>Sanding product manager for expertise in sanding machinery.</p> <p>Types of Resources: Physical, intellectual, human.</p>	<p>Automation of the sanding process with robots to alleviate human operators from dangerous tasks.</p> <p>Characteristics: Performance, customization, risk reduction.</p>	<p>Cooperative alliances with partners for a more productive, efficient solution minimizing human effort.</p>	<p>Targeting manufacturing companies, industrial facilities, and research institutions.</p> <p>Customer Base: Segmented market focusing on industrial automation solutions.</p>
			<u>Channels</u>	
			<p>Direct sales, online platforms, partner networks for distribution.</p> <p>Industry trade shows and events, webinars, and online tutorials for engagement and education.</p> <p>Integration with Customer Routines: Through direct engagement and educational efforts.</p>	
<u>Cost Structure</u>	<u>Revenue Streams</u>			
<p>Includes research and development, production and manufacturing costs, partnership and collaboration fees, marketing and sales expenses, operational costs.</p> <p>Business: Value-driven, focusing on continuous product improvement and premium value proposition.</p>	<p>Direct sales of the autonomous sanding solution.</p> <p>Service and maintenance contracts for ongoing support.</p> <p>Licensing fees for proprietary software.</p> <p>Pricing: Likely a mix of asset sale and subscription fees for services and software.</p>			

2.12.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

Table 66: SWOT Analysis Ex. Out. #12

Use Case 5	Version 1.0	Owner: ROB, SCM	Date: 04/04/2024
S	Strengths	W	Weaknesses
<p>Innovative Solution. the autonomous sanding process represents a cutting-edge solution, relieving human operators from hazardous tasks.</p> <p>Strong Partnerships. Collaborations with SCM, FOKUS, and other OASEES consortium members leverage collective expertise.</p> <p>Integrated Approach. The combination of the mobile robot, robotic arm, and sanding tool for a complete sanding solution showcases the ability to deliver automation systems.</p>		<p>Complex Implementation. Integrating technologies from multiple partners into a unique system can present challenges in terms of compatibility, implementation time, and costs.</p> <p>Specialized Market. The focus on automating the sanding process in industrial settings may limit market reach.</p> <p>Dependence on Partners. The project’s success relies on the cooperation and contributions of several members, which might affect timelines.</p>	
O	Opportunities	T	Threats
<p>Market Demand for Automation. Increasing demand for automation in industrial processes opens up market opportunities.</p> <p>Technological Advancements. Ongoing advancements in robotics and AI offer potential for continuous improvement.</p> <p>Sustainability Trends. A growing emphasis on sustainable practices may drive demand for automated solutions.</p>		<p>Competitive Market. The industrial automation sector is highly competitive, with numerous companies offering similar solutions.</p> <p>Technological Obsolescence. Rapid technological change poses a risk that the solution could become outdated if not continuously updated with the latest advancements.</p> <p>Economic Fluctuations. Economic downturns can lead to reduced capital expenditure budgets among target customer segments, potentially affecting sales of high-cost automation solutions like ours.</p>	

2.12.3 VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

Table 67 : VPC Analysis Ex .Out. #12

Benefits	Description	Wants	Description
Enhanced Efficiency & Safety	The solution enhances the sanding process in terms of automation, productivity, health hazards, and quality	Streamlining Industrial Processes	Companies seek an automated solution that meshes with existing operations, cuts down on manual labor, and elevates product consistency
Features	Description	Needs	Description

Advanced Automation Solution	With its combination of a mobile robot, robotic arm, and precise sanding tool, the solution is designed for straightforward integration into industrial environments	Meeting Industrial Needs	The industry demands a dependable, efficient, and cost-effective automation solution for tedious and dangerous tasks
Experience	Description	Fears	Description
Seamless Transition Experience	The solution eases the adoption of automation technology with its user-friendly interface and customer support	Overcoming Automation Anxiety	Potential adopters may be apprehensive about the integration complexity, uncertain ROI on the initial investment, and the rapid obsolescence of new technology
Ideal Customer	Description	Substitutes	Description
Future-Focused Facility	The perfect customer is an innovative industrial entity eager to enhance efficiency and safety through technology, and keen on automating labor-intensive jobs	Alternatives and Competitors	Alternatives range from conventional manual labor and semi-automatic machines to other automated systems that might not offer the full integration of mobile robotics and analytics, potentially presenting lower upfront costs

Table 68 : VPC Ex. Out. #12

Value Proposition Canvas		Designed for:	Designed by:	Date:	Version:
<p>Benefits</p> <p>A benefit is what your product does for the customer. The benefits are the ways that the features make your customer's life easier by increasing pleasure or decreasing pain. The benefits of your product are the really core of your value proposition. The best way to list out the benefits of your product on the canvas is to imagine all the ways that your product makes your customer's life better.</p>	<p>Experience</p> <p>The product experience is the way that owning your product makes the customer feel. It's the sum total of the combined features and benefits. Product experience is different to features and benefits because it's more about the emotional reasons why people buy your product and what it means for them in their own lives. The product experience is the kernel that will help identify the market positioning and brand essence that is usually built out of the value proposition.</p>	<p>Wants</p> <p>The emotional drivers of decision-making are things that we want to be, do or have. Our wants are usually conscious (but aspirational) thoughts about how we'd like to improve our lives. They sometimes seem like daydreams but they can be powerful motivators of action. The wants speak more to the pull of our hearts and our emotions.</p>	<p>Fears</p> <p>Fears can be a strong driver of purchasing behaviour and can be the hidden source of wants and needs. For any product there is a secret "pain of switching". Even if your product is better than the competition, it might not be a big enough improvement to overcome the inertia of the status quo.</p>		
<p>Features</p> <p>A feature is a factual description of how your product works. The features are the functioning attributes of your product.</p>		<p>Needs</p> <p>The customer's needs are the rational things that the customer needs to get done. Interestingly, needs are not always conscious. Customers can have needs that they may not know about yet. Designers call these "latent needs". The needs speak more to the pull of our heads and rational motivations.</p>			
<p>Product</p> <p>Name your product or service</p>	<p>Ideal Customer</p> <p>Name your ideal customer</p>	<p>Substitutes</p> <p>These are not just the obvious competitors, but also existing behaviours and coping mechanisms. Remember that people made it this far in life without your product. If your product isn't better than the existing solutions then you don't have a real-world value proposition.</p>			

2.13 EXPLOITABLE OUTCOME #13 - OTE

Infrastructure inspection and monitoring and 3D modeling with the use of drone’s swarms over 5G.

Table 69: Exploitable Outcome #13

Owner	OTE – Mobile Network operator responsible for providing connectivity, network infrastructure and data federation and sovereignty in distributed edge computing
Contributors	NCSR, IMEC, NKUA, Infrachain, InQbit, Tecnalia
Ownership per Implementation	N/A
Protection Measures	N/A
Usage Rights	N/A
Licensing Information	License for the spectrum bands,
Notes	N/A

2.13.1 BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS

Table 70: BMC Analysis Ex. Out. #13

Key Partners	Role
OASEES Partners	OASEES Platform Development
UC3 partners	NCSR: Leader of UC3, Infrastructure provider for UC3, development and deployment of DAO, Smart contracts, and SDKs,
NCSR Demokritos, IMEC	IMEC: Provider of HW accelerated vision/radar, and resource allocation algorithms in support of accelerators
NKUA	Development of algorithms of machine learning and federated learning. Participation in the development of the OASEES Software Development Kit (SDK)
Intrachain	DAO and Smart contracts development and deployment.
Infili	Smart node connectivity mechanism, distributed-learning algorithms for secure edge analytics
InQbit	Self Sovereign Identity (SSI) for a portable digital identity.

Tecnalía	Data sovereignty, Data Product orientation
UAV manufacturers and operators	
Key Activities	Description
Provision of connectivity services	Provide 5G connectivity tailored the OASEES projects' needs.
Addressing data federation and sovereignty in distributed edge computing	Applying mechanisms for securing the resources and preserving data privacy and sovereignty across the IoT to-edge-to-cloud compute continuum
Dissemination and communication of the project results maximizing the impact of the project	We disseminate and communicate the projects results through conferences, meetings, workshops press releases, website and our social media accounts
Key Resources	Description
Mobile and Fixed Network.	OTE is an operator of communication network and owner of network infrastructure offering optimized services for drone operation
Infrastructure and connectivity for drones and equipment	Components for the compute and connect infrastructure are for example 5G RAN, UPF for MEC, MEC, drones etc.
Employees with high technical expertise in various domains	Data scientists, Network Engineers, IT Engineers, Business Analysts
Wide network of partnerships/communication channels	Telecom Vendors, Cloud Providers, SMEs, Software application providers etc.
Value Propositions	Description
Value delivered to customers	Predictive maintenance, 3D modelling for urban planning like coverage service for network planning, reduced costs for operation and maintenance, reduced risks for remote or challenging-to-access areas, high-level techniques (AI/ML), for processing and analysing the data, high QoS
Customer's problems are we helping to solve Inspection of infrastructure in areas that are difficult to reach 3D visualisation with high resolution cameras	Autonomous drone inspections gather high-resolution aerial data, generate accurate 3D models, and a suitable antennae position to help tower businesses extend their infrastructure. Health monitoring of infrastructure address problems before they become a cause of disruption or malfunction, which enhancing efficiency for both the organisation and the customer

<p>Bundles of products and services are offering.</p> <p>End-to-end solution for capture, storage, and analysis of inspection data</p> <p>Secure data sharing</p> <p>3D modelling for urban/network planning</p> <p>Predictive maintenance</p>	<p>MNOs can use its own fleet of drones for the data collection, provide data storage in cloud and application hosting for the analysis of the data.</p> <p>5G offers high speed large capacity network for the transmission of high-quality video and images that can be used for 3D visualisation.</p> <p>Predictive maintenance from the analysis of the data captured from drones</p>
<p>Satisfaction needs</p>	<p>Reduced Cost, Data collection in real-time allows rapid decision making. High QoS and QoE, Secure Data sharing</p>
<p>Customer Relationships</p>	<p>Description</p>
<p>OTE invest in technological excellence of network to enhance connectivity and quality of services for best customer experience.in close collaboration with its partners. The infrastructure</p>	<p>Meetings and cooperation with the stakeholders and communication with customers through various channels</p>
<p>Channels</p>	<p>Description</p>
<p>Conferences, Workshops, Demonstrations</p> <p>Meetings with the stakeholders</p> <p>Website, social media accounts, Press releases</p>	<p>Establish cooperative relationships with the stakeholders</p>
<p>Sales</p>	<p>Direct sales to companies, Sales via Key partners</p>
<p>Customer Segments</p>	<p>Description</p>
<p>Telecommunication Industries</p> <p>Energy Industries</p> <p>Power generation companies</p>	<p>Drone technology allows the inspection of infrastructure such as power lines, pipelines, and communication towers.</p>
<p>Cost Structure</p>	<p>Description</p>
<p>5G Network components, 5G connectivity to the drones, drones, cameras, sensors</p> <p>Licenses for software,</p> <p>Human resources: Analysts, technicians, researchers, and developers</p>	<p>5G RAN, UPF, MEC for the Non-Public Network</p> <p>Unmanned Aerial System UAS</p> <p>Engineers for deployment, operation and maintenance of the service</p>
<p>Revenue Streams</p>	<p>Description</p>
<p>Connectivity Services</p> <p>Advanced Services Provisioning for inspection, monitoring and 3D visualization.</p> <p>Collecting & monetizing data for interested parties.</p>	<p>Provider of connectivity Services for live-streaming video, HD images transfers and the UAVs</p> <p>Services for inspections. monitoring and planning include hardware, collection of data, processing, reporting, and insights.</p>

Subscription for hardware and software related to the inspection and 3D modeling, Expert assistance	Technicians for deployment, operation and maintenance of the service
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2.13.2 SWOT ANALYSIS

Table 71: SWOT Analysis Ex. Out. #13

<p>S Strengths</p> <p>What are your key competencies and strengths?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The use of drones for inspections, and monitoring is an effective solution for remote or challenging-to-access areas that cannot be reached by traditional means or are unsafe to approach due to potential risks and can reduce the costs for operation and maintenance of infrastructures and can also be used for network planning. OTE is the biggest ICT solutions integrator in Greece, with extensive expertise gained from successfully executing large-scale and complex projects¹ 	<p>W Weaknesses</p> <p>What areas require improvement or show vulnerabilities?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A highly competitive and dynamic market. Other operators may provide similar solutions. Effective for defects with high occurrence, difficult to detect rare defect types (lack of data) Few existing open-source datasets for damage detection and network planning
<p>O Opportunities</p> <p>What unique resources or advantages can you leverage?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5G networks are designed to offer improved bandwidth and ultra-low latency. 5G NR-RedCap supports devices with lower cost/complexity, smaller physical size, and longer battery life. 5G reduces end-to-end latency and provides better user experience (QoS) 5G network's high bandwidth guarantees the fast and reliable transmission of high-quality images and videos captured by the high-definition cameras of drones and to the control center for analysis Faster streaming services through edge computing 	<p>T Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How do others perceive potential challenges or threats to your organization or project? Competitive solutions offered by other market players such as other operators, and hyperscalers. Few existing open-source datasets for damage detection and network planning Challenging weather conditions Limitation is the regulatory framework around drone operations

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telco MEC Platform allows the distributed storage and processing of drone payload data, such as images and videos, in addition to any control functionality. • 5G network slicing allows drone related communications to be separated from other network traffic, permitting higher QoS measures, supporting enhanced data privacy and security for drones. • Autonomous capabilities and interconnectivity with other drones make it more efficient to operate fleets of drones. 	
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2.13.3 VALUE PROPOSITION CANVAS

Table 72: VPC Ex. Out. #13

Benefits	Description	Wants	Description
<p>Better monitoring and inspection procedures</p> <p>Extend the lifespan of infrastructure and assets. 3D visualization is a powerful tool which can help planners discover issues and opportunities and choose the most effective way to allocate resources</p>	<p>Drones are able to perform inspections without the need for human intervention, which lowers the possibility of human error and increases inspection efficiency.</p> <p>3D modelling simplifies the process to identify potential obstacles, determine the distance between neighbouring antennas, and obtain local permissions. Tower companies can adjust the location of their sites to meet the demands of urban 5G networks</p>	<p>Cost reduction,</p> <p>Reduced risks,</p> <p>Reliable infrastructure</p> <p>Rapid decision making</p>	<p>Edge computing allows real-time filtering and prioritization of data captured. Only critical data is sent to the central server for further analysis, reducing bandwidth usage and improving overall efficiency. Better resource management.</p> <p>Real-time data on battery health and power consumption can be analysed at the edge for flight path optimization and energy usage minimization.</p> <p>Inspection and monitoring by human workers is more prone to errors because performance is affected by human factors such as distraction, lack of</p>

			awareness, lack of knowledge and fatigue
Features	Description	Needs	Description
<p>Low Latency</p> <p>Near real-time data processing</p> <p>Increased security and data privacy</p> <p>Access to difficult to reach areas.</p> <p>Safer, agile, and less costly compared to traditional methods (human workers)</p> <p>Secure Data sharing</p>	<p>5G Networks enable operators to monitor live video transmissions from drones assist in drone identification, route planning, remote control and location tracking</p>	<p>Reduced CAPEX/OPEX</p> <p>High QoS,</p> <p>Predictive maintenance</p>	<p>Reduced CAPEX and OPEX through improved resource management and virtualization at the edge-cloud continuum</p> <p>5G offers high bandwidth and low latency, which significantly improves QoS.</p> <p>AI software and 3D scanning offers high accuracy in identifying defects of the infrastructure and offers a proactive maintenance strategy to predict equipment failures before they occur</p>
Experience	Description	Fears	Description
<p>5G connectivity offers to Uncrewed Aerial Systems (UAS), wide coverage, high reliability and QoS, robust security, and seamless mobility</p> <p>Ability to visualize buildings, structures, and landscapes beyond 2D representations and improve the process of planning in urban areas</p>		<p>Technical failure</p>	<p>The main fears are those related to technical failure, in which the system integration and system performance is not able to achieve and meet the target KPIs.</p>
Ideal Customer	Description	Substitutes	Description
<p>Telecommunication Industries</p> <p>Energy Industries</p> <p>Power generation companies</p>	<p>Drones help the telecom sector inspect communication equipment and cell towers, providing uninterrupted service and lowering the possibility of outages. Drones can be used also for Radio</p>	<p>Human workers</p> <p>2D visualization</p> <p>Centralized control of the drones</p>	<p>Inspection and monitoring by human workers is more prone to errors because performance is affected by human factors such as distraction, lack of</p>

<p>Network planning and determine the ideal location of new antenna</p> <p>Drones are employed in the energy sector to monitor solar panels, wind turbines, and power cables. This makes it possible for energy businesses to find and fix issues, maximize efficiency, and guarantee the reliability of their infrastructure.</p>	<p>awareness, lack of knowledge and fatigue</p>
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Table 73 : VPC Ex. Out. #13

<i>Designed for:</i> <i>Designed by:</i> <i>Date:</i> <i>Version:</i>			
Value Proposition Canvas			
<p>Benefits</p> <p>Better monitoring and inspection procedures</p> <p>Secure data sharing</p> <p>Extend the lifespan of infrastructure and assets. 3D visualization is a powerful tool which can help planners discover issues and opportunities and make informed resource allocation decisions. Advanced artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms for enhanced decision-</p>	<p>Experience</p> <p>5G connectivity offers to Uncrewed Aerial Systems (UAS), wide coverage, high reliability and QoS, robust security, and seamless mobility</p> <p>Ability to visualize buildings, structures, and landscapes beyond 2D representations and improve the process of planning in urban areas</p>	<p>Wants</p> <p>Cost effective solution for inspection and monitoring of infrastructure</p> <p>Access to difficult to reach areas</p> <p>Secure communications</p>	<p>Fears</p> <p>Technical failures</p> <p>Poor network coverage in certain areas</p> <p>Insufficient open-source datasets for damage detection and network planning</p>

<p>making and obstacle avoidance</p>			
<p>Features</p> <p>Low Latency Near real-time data processing Increased security and data privacy Access to difficult to reach areas. Safer, agile, and less costly compared to traditional methods (human workers, centralized control of drones)</p>		<p>Needs</p> <p>High QoS, Reduced OPEX</p>	
<p>Product</p> <p>Product/Service</p> <p>Infrastructure inspection and monitoring and 3D modeling for network planning with the use of drone's swarms over 5G</p>	<p>Ideal Customer</p> <p>Telecommunication Industries Energy Industries Power generation companies</p>	<p>Substitutes</p> <p>Human workers Centralized control for drone swarms (for flight management)</p>	

The OASEES SDK, developed as part of the OASEES project, stands out as a major innovation in managing computing tasks over networks of devices, commonly known as edge computing. It offers a set of tools that make it easier to deploy and manage applications across various devices, crucial for businesses and organizations that handle a lot of data across many locations.

Key Features of the OASEES SDK

Feature	Description
Multi-platform Support	Works smoothly with different systems, including cloud services and local devices, thanks to standardized connections.
Modular Architecture	Users can customize their setup by choosing specific parts of the SDK based on their needs, adding flexibility.
Automation and Orchestration	Simplifies complex tasks like setting up applications and adjusting their scale, reducing the need for manual input.

Potential for Future Use

Potential Use	Description
Commercialization	Companies could use the SDK to develop new products or improve existing ones, especially for data processing across many locations.
Collaborations and Partnerships	Could serve as a foundation for partnerships with tech companies, universities, or industry groups to expand its features or integrate with other technologies.
Academic and Research Applications	Useful in universities and research centers for teaching or projects exploring new technologies in edge computing.
Open Source Community Development	Releasing it as open-source could attract global developers who can enhance the SDK collaboratively.
Standards Development	Helpful in refining global standards for edge computing based on real-world usage and feedback.

To maximize the SDK's post-project exploitation, several strategies could be adopted:

Market Analysis and Engagement: Conduct thorough market research to identify industries and sectors where the SDK could have the most significant impact. Engaging with potential customers early can help tailor the SDK to meet market demands.

Demonstration Projects: Implementing demonstration projects that showcase the SDK's capabilities and benefits in real-world scenarios can serve as powerful marketing tools and help in attracting commercial interest.

Training and Certification Programs: Developing training programs to certify users and developers on the SDK can help in building a knowledgeable user base, encouraging wider adoption.

Continued Innovation: Continue investing in research and development to ensure the SDK remains at the technological forefront, incorporating the latest advancements in edge computing, AI, and IoT.

OASEES PILOT SUCCESS STORIES

Use case 1: Smart Edge-Connected Node for the Analysis of Voice, Articulation and Fluency Disorders in Parkinson Disease:

Data collection for this use case has been started based on a standard research protocol validated by the French Commission on Information Technology and Liberties (CNIL) responsible for privacy, individual rights, and public liberties. The gathered speech samples from patients suffering from Parkinson's Disease (PD) are based on identical sets of stimuli used in speech therapy and annotated manually by speech therapists in order to obtain the different international and speech profiles of intelligibility. This allows to set-up scores related to the severity of dysarthria in PD patients – an important measure for training of the algorithms used in the OASEES project. Based on this data, the first version of the edge device using the OASEES stack with a specially trained algorithm has been set-up. Currently, the device is tested and further improved to perform in a similar way as speech therapists during the assessment of the disease severity the next step the various interfaces need to be developed allowing the different stakeholders to easily access the system. In the long run, it is considered to provide a fully annotated dataset for research purposes and further improvement of the system using third-party algorithms.

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS AND BEST PRACTISES

DATA ACT

The European data strategy seeks to establish a single market for data in order to ensure the data sovereignty and global competitiveness of Europe. ¹The Data Act is a cornerstone of the data strategy in Europe. Its primary goal is to position Europe as a leader in the data economy by utilising the vast amounts of data to the advantage of its economy and society. The purpose of the Data Act is to increase the reusability of business data by establishing regulations regarding who may access and use particular data, as well as for what purposes. This is accomplished through the establishment of policies regulating the access and use of data produced inside the European Union, covering all economic sectors. The primary goal of the Act is to increase the availability of data for and within sectoral data spaces, thereby fostering a competitive data market and advancing innovation driven by data.

The Data Act involves regulations that enable users of interconnected devices to obtain access to the data they generate and share such data with third parties. It also provides public sector institutions the authority to access and utilise data held by private companies in specific situations, for example emergency situations. Furthermore, it aims to change the power dynamics in data sharing contracts by reducing the exploitation of contractual imbalances, thereby benefiting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Lastly, it helps customers in moving between various providers of cloud data processing services.²

The European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge, and Cloud promotes next-generation edge and cloud technology.

The European Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge, and Cloud is based on the European Data Strategy that has been in place since February 2020. The establishment of this initiative was officially supported by the European Council conclusions in October 2020, as well as the Declaration on European Cloud, which was signed by all Member States in October 2020 and published in the updated European Industrial Strategy in May 2021. The Alliance was established in July 2021 and started activities in December 2021.

The Alliance unites corporations, Member States, and experts in the field. It supports EU enterprises and public bodies that process sensitive data and strives to boost Europe's industrial data leadership and gain advantage on cloud and edge technology. Europe's digital transformation relies on cloud and edge technologies as they play a crucial role for promoting the adoption of developing technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and 5G. The Alliance brings together business and governmental stakeholders to establish strategic investment roadmaps for the next generation of highly secure, distributed, interoperable, and resource-efficient computing technologies. In addition, the Alliance will assist with cloud governance exchanges, such as public cloud procurement.¹

IPCEI-CIS Important Projects of Common European Interest- Next Generation Cloud Infrastructure and Services

European Union supports the creation of a federated data management system in order existing data resources can be utilised efficiently and data processing capacities can be optimised. Consequently, the implementation of sustainable energy-efficient data utilisation, real-time data provision capability, ultra-secure data communication, and new data processing services will enable the development of new business models.

IPCEIs will contribute significantly to the European Union's economy and industry competitiveness, employment, the green and digital transition, and economic development. By bringing together economic actors, financial resources, knowledge, and expertise from across the Union, IPCEIs enable the generation of positive residual impacts for the entire Union.²

On 5 December 2023, the European Commission approved the IPCEI Next Generation Cloud Infrastructure and Services (CIS)³. The primary objective of IPCEI-CIS (IPCEI Next Generation Cloud Infrastructure and Services) is to strengthen the digital and technological sovereignty of Europe. Currently, 12 Member States are collaborating under the German Council Presidency to develop a robust and environmentally friendly "Multi-Provider Cloud-Edge Continuum" which is not relying on a single provider. The IPCEI will leverage existing initiatives on EU and national level especially the GAIA-X open source architectural framework.⁴

The term "Cloud-Edge Continuum" describes the smooth integration of edge and cloud computing, which facilitates enhanced data processing and storage in distributed networks. Data and applications can be strategically positioned either at the edge locations, which are in close proximity to the end devices, or in the cloud, depending on specific needs and demands.

The project aims to enhance data processing capabilities by developing software and data sharing tools. These tools will enable the use of federated, energy-efficient, and trustworthy cloud and edge distributed data processing

¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cloud-alliance>

² https://competition-policy.ec.europa.eu/state-aid/ipcei_en

³ https://competition-policy.ec.europa.eu/state-aid/ipcei/approved-ipceis/cloud_en

⁴ https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/EN/Downloads/1/ipcei-cis-value-chain-description.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=1

technologies and services. The IPCEI CIS project will provide a wide range of opportunities for European enterprises and citizens, promoting the Digital and Green transition in Europe.⁵

SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE

Data is a vital resource for economic growth, competitiveness, innovation job generation, and overall improvements in society. The increased volume, variety, social and economic significance of data indicates a fundamental change towards a data-driven socio-economic model. Data Economy depends on a shared framework of trust that allows for the creation of single market and common dataspace for the free flow of non-personal data across borders and sectors and between businesses, academia, relevant stakeholders and the public sector.

The exponential increase in data generation makes the effectiveness of cloud and edge facilities across Europe crucial. This will be accomplished through the implementation of outstanding operating and management software and enhanced connectivity ensuring security, resource efficiency, interoperability and multi-provider services.

Europe aims to strengthen its technological sovereignty by improving data processing capabilities and satisfy the demand for next-generation data processing infrastructures through the integration of edge computing, IoT, and cloud. Furthermore, it introduces a novel framework for intelligence and data processing, both at the edge and on the device level. Processing must be located in closer proximity to the location where the data is generated in order to mitigate concerns related to latency, security, privacy, and sustainability.

5G and edge computing has proven synergistic and mutually beneficial. 5G offers improved speeds, increased throughput, and reduced latency compared to earlier cellular technologies. The integration of 5G Core services and open (or virtualized) RANs enables the provision of edge computing, whether it is for many tenants or for a private edge deployment. Furthermore, the decentralised structure of telecommunications networks, together with the concepts of data value and data sovereignty, presents an opportunity for AI to assist in efficiently managing the complexity and automating the lifecycles of these networks.

Telecommunication companies are deploying Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) at the edge of their mobile networks to drive the development and use of innovative use cases that need ultra-low latency, the ability to support massive numbers of real-time IoT connections, and faster mobile broadband connections.

MEC is described as a system that offers cloud computing capabilities and an IT service environment at the edge of an access network that includes one or more access technologies, near to its customers. MEC can enhance end-user experience by reducing service interruptions, end-to-end latencies, enhancing security and data privacy, and enabling intelligent edge services. This is achieved by leveraging optimal cloud deployment strategies such as edge load balancing, secure messaging across various cloud environments, and using AI/ML services through distributed cloud infrastructure. After the establishment of extensive Wide Area Networks and large-scale infrastructure, the advantages of Edge Computing will strengthen the potential of 5G and create opportunities for a variety of novel and improved use cases such as real-time drone fleet management, autonomous control of robots and vehicles, energy management, healthcare, entertainment, personal assistance, monitoring, security, surveillance, and predictive maintenance.

The OASEES project identified the need for an innovative, broad, and transformative strategy concerning the cloud-to-edge continuum, swarm programmability and support for trustworthy, secure, interoperable, and multi-tenant deployments. Service sharing across edge-based distributed infrastructures is an important feature of OASEES that requires a cross-layer orchestration mechanism between storage, network, and computation services leveraging the capabilities of edge nodes. One of the main objectives of the OASEES project is to provide a set of desired services as presented in the identified use cases and smart edge node connectivity to fully utilize the cloud, edge and IoT continuum.

⁵ <https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/EN/Artikel/Industry/ipcei-cis.html>

5G networks are very capable of supporting the development and operation of drones and related drone services. Drones have advantages for a variety of commercial applications such as inspection, monitoring and surveillance, especially in remote or hard-to-reach areas where safety issues are a concern, such as locations with tall structures (e.g., high masts, transmitters, wind turbines) or areas that extend over a long distance. Mobile networks provide wider and more reliable connectivity, allowing drones to fly farther and operate autonomously over longer distances. 5G mobile networks offer significantly faster data transfer speeds compared to traditional Wi-Fi based control systems used in drones.⁶ This allows for real-time transmission of high-resolution video feeds, sensor data and control commands with minimal latency. Live streaming of sensor data, including images, videos and other relevant information, enables the operator to evaluate this data while the drone is in flight and perform necessary actions to make sure all necessary inspections are performed and that the right data is acquired.⁷

Drones can be equipped with a variety of sensors beyond just cameras. Thermal cameras can detect hot spots that might indicate overheating equipment. LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) sensors can create 3D models⁸ of structures to identify temperature anomalies detection which are very crucial for the Telecom industry. AI algorithms that have been trained to detect patterns and anomalies that could indicate potential issues can be trained on the data collected by drones. Predictive Maintenance, leveraging AI algorithms, provides effective solutions for determining the timing, location and reasons behind maintenance tasks.

⁶ <https://www.gsma.com/iot/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/2021-03-GSMA-5G-Industry-4.0-Op-Tech-Networks.pdf>

⁷ <https://www.gsma.com/iot/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Drone-Benefits-Analysis-Report-final.pdf>

⁸ Zhang, Zhengxin, and Lixue Zhu. 2023. "A Review on Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Remote Sensing: Platforms, Sensors, Data Processing Methods, and Applications" *Drones* 7, no. 6: 398. <https://doi.org/10.3390/drones7060398>

SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

CONTEXT

In the rapidly evolving landscape of secure data sharing, OASEES distinguishes itself with robust plans for sustainability and scalability. With a keen understanding of market dynamics and the utilization of state-of-the-art technology, OASEES aims to make a lasting impression.

OASEES is deeply committed to long-term sustainability. Since its inception, the project has been strategically aligned with emerging trends and evolving consumer behaviors, ensuring its continued relevance in a dynamic market. By identifying and seizing opportunities for growth and expansion, OASEES establishes a strong presence in a competitive environment. Through strategic partnerships with key stakeholders and a steadfast commitment to legal compliance, OASEES not only navigates regulatory complexities but also cultivates collaborative networks conducive to long-term success. Furthermore, OASEES's sustainability efforts are closely intertwined with its environmental consciousness. By adopting eco-friendly technologies and responsible resource management practices, the project minimizes its environmental impact while maximizing efficiency. This dedication to sustainability goes beyond mere compliance, embodying a proactive stance towards environmental stewardship that resonates with stakeholders and consumers alike.

In a world characterized by rapid technological advancements and evolving user expectations, OASEES's capacity for growth is paramount. Built upon a foundation of robust infrastructure and modular architecture, the project can easily accommodate increasing demands and adapt to changes. As market dynamics evolve and user requirements shift, OASEES remains steadfast in its commitment to innovation and adaptability, ensuring seamless scalability without compromising performance or quality. Moreover, OASEES's scalability extends beyond technical capabilities to encompass strategic partnerships and collaborative frameworks. By fostering dynamic ecosystems of industry partners, academic institutions, and regulatory bodies, the project harnesses collective expertise and resources to fuel its growth trajectory. This approach not only enhances OASEES's scalability but also reinforces its resilience in the face of external challenges and uncertainties.

Ultimately, OASEES's sustainability and scalability represent more than just strategic imperatives; they signify a dedication to lasting impact and transformative change. By staying attuned to market trends and continuously seeking opportunities for improvement, OASEES is at the forefront of secure data sharing, making a positive societal impact and shaping the future of the industry.

INDIVIDUAL EXPLOITATION PLAN

This section provides an exploitation plan from each partner.

NATIONAL CENTER FOR SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH “DEMOKRITOS”

NCSR is actively deploying an exploitation plan for OASEES, leveraging the state-of-the-art technology developed to commercialize and bring to market edge computing solutions. The center currently licenses the innovative technologies emerging from OASEES, partners with industry leaders, and fosters startups within the ecosystem of Lefkippos Technology Park. This technology park serves as a vibrant hub for innovation and entrepreneurship, where NCSR facilitates the incubation of new SMEs to get accustomed with Web3.0 technologies through OASEES. It encourages collaboration between researchers and commercial entities to tailor

applications for smart cities, healthcare, and industrial sectors. In parallel, NCSR is engaging with standardization bodies, advocating for the integration of OASEES framework into emerging standards, thus influencing global protocols and ensuring wide-scale interoperability and adoption, through its involvement in ETSI MEC Security group. These activities not only position NCSR as a pivotal player in edge computing but also enhance the technological capacity and reputation of Lefkippos Technology Park as a cradle of cutting-edge research and development.

INTERUNIVERSITAIR MICRO-ELECTRONICA CENTRUM (IMEC)

As part of the OASEES framework development, imec contributions will be open-sourced, and as such available for the European research community. Future extensions of the software components developed by imec, will also remain open for the public. This involves functionality related to the orchestration of accelerator components.

TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION CENTER

Tecnalia mission is to transform technological research into prosperity. We are agents of transformation of companies and society for their adaptation to the challenges of a changing future. Tecnalia will exploit the results from OASEES within the Public Authorities and Private sector to foster the digital transformation of both sectors. Tecnalia will also use its participated subsidiary Tecnalia Ventures to exploit any result from OASEES that could be further industrialized to become a commercial asset. The current potential assets that could become part of its product portfolio are the Data Product onboarding in Gaia—X as well as the Blockchain Based Broker.

COMMISSARIAT ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVES (CEA)

Technology transfer to French and EU industrial partners. New Human Factors knowledge will be used to scout new applications, as well as for educational purposes and to advance an edge-connected health system for neurodegenerative rehabilitation processes, which will be offered to the industry for further development and implementation.

FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FÖRDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV (FOKUS)

Fraunhofer FOKUS works on building the high-level Quantum Software Development Kit **QRISP** to leverage the potential of quantum computers and make it easier accessible for non-physicists. This will especially enable small and medium enterprises to assess the potential quantum technologies, and quantum computers in particular, could have for their business models.

ETHNIKO KAI KAPODISTRIAKO PANEPISTIMIO ATHINON(NKUA)

NKUA foresees three important routes towards exploitation of the results. The first is focusing on exploiting OASEES results in education; the second focuses on enriching the scientific status of the involved personnel; and the third one is targeting on exploiting the project outcomes in future research projects. On the first exploitation strand, OASEES will help extend the undergraduate and MSc courses, while introducing new research topics on secure orchestration of highly demanding applications with AI/ML approaches, for the creation of modern and innovative PhD dissertations. With respect to the second exploitation strand, NKUA sees the participation in OASEES as a clear step towards the exploitation of the technical and scientific advancements, which will be developed in close collaboration with the rest of the project partners. The interest is mainly focused in the areas of decentralized AI applications where the involved personnel have a remarkable research record and relevant publications. Thus, the participation in OASEES will help the faculty to further strengthen its position in the

relevant competitive research areas. Finally, with respect to the third exploitation field, NKUA will leverage the outcomes of this project and build upon the gained expertise to be exploited in new research projects that would give the opportunity to further promote research in these areas. The NKUA involvement in a highly innovative project with industrial partnerships will allow its establishment as a significant European research and development organization and it will increase the visibility, recognition, and publication record of the University. Therefore, NKUA will stay competitive for future research projects and initiatives and strengthen its position as a University (knowledge, scientific quality, facilities).

ROBOTNIK AUTOMATION SLL

Robotnik's objective extends to refining our products and offering more automated solutions, among other enhancements. This ambition underscores our commitment to delivering advanced, efficient, and highly integrated automation capabilities within the OASEES ecosystem and beyond.

INQBIT INNOVATIONS SRL

InQbit seeks to leverage the initiatives undertaken in OASEES by contributing to scientific publications and conducting additional research and development focused on enhancing authentication and authorization mechanisms for both users and devices. This effort aims to strengthen the cybersecurity services aspect, which constitutes a core component of IQB's business model individual exploitation activities by each partner

INFRACHAIN ASBL

Infracchain aims to leverage the decentralized nature of OASEES use case, exploiting DAO, to enhance data availability, facilitate various use cases exploiting the OASEES' development stack, and foster new cases by leveraging blockchain technology and smart contracts.

EMOTION SRL

EMOT, as a charging station manufacturer, charging point operator and eMobility services provider, intends to exploit OASEES solutions to increase its products and services value, both from electric vehicle users and electric grid operators point of view. Moreover, EMOT will exploit the participation in the OASEES project to improve its staff proficiency, both from a technical and social point of view, thanks to the collaboration with the consortium partners. From the beginning, EMOT designed its charging stations as IoT devices, strongly believing that it allows to offer useful services to customers, from real-time monitoring to remote management. In the context of OASEES project, EMOT tests smart charging solutions by exploiting energy forecasting system based on machine learning technologies with the aim of reducing charging sessions impact on electricity network and, at the same time, helping to efficiently integrate intermittent renewable energies into the grid acting as an energy flexibility source to balance the grid via a DLT/blockchain decentralized P2P marketplace.

ASM TERNI SPA

Due to the high penetration of DER, ASM faces severe network stability problems to the local power grid and seeks to use the OASEES developments to reduce curtailment due to the active reverse power and match energy demand to availability. Advanced computational tools able to actively involve the local electric mobility for absorbing the surplus of green energy produced locally will be exploited by ASM to create new business models and work opportunities.

ADRESTIA RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT

Adrestia recognizes that in order to maximize the efficacy of creative ideas, cooperation, and knowledge exchange are crucial. Because of this, we are committed to establishing partnerships and pilot projects that enable us to collaborate with well-known businesses, educational institutions, and governmental organizations. Through active collaboration on projects, workshop organization, and dissemination campaigns, Adrestia seeks to raise awareness among academics as a whole. In addition, we collaborate with academia and industry to maximize the societal and economic impact of the OASEES project, and we participate in and exchange knowledge about it (subject to technical team approval).

INSTITUT HOPALE BERCK

No input to provide at this moment.

SENSO ENGINEERING BV

Senso Engineering will foster cooperation, and especially awareness, on the topics of earthquake preparedness and recovery. Protection of people and businesses against earthquakes, which is the deadliest of all natural disasters, is of prime importance in Europe but also in the world. Senso, through cooperation with technology developers, sensor producers, and end-users, will stimulate a better preparedness for the earthquake events. Furthermore, through radically new concepts in the industry, most of which are/will be developed and tested within OASEES, such as use of AI for earthquake signal recognition, experiments on using quantum technology for large scale post-earthquake estimations, or pushing the earthquake decision support to the edge, By using platforms such as conferences, workshops, exhibitions, meetings and publications, Senso is hoping to have a significant positive impact on the sensor companies, hardware and software developers, and end-users in tackling with the huge challenge of earthquake resilience.

INFILI TECHNOLOGIES SOCIETE ANONYME

Infili aims at exploiting the efforts within OASEES in the form of scientific publications, further research and development in the direction of advanced and adaptable vulnerability-detection for smart contracts in order to enhance cybersecurity and security-analytics services which are part of Infili's business model.

SCM GROUP SPA

SCM will exploit the project results implementing the features of its existing products. SCM aims to add solutions developed in OASEES project to its current technological offer for customers, providing innovative solutions for flexible, customized and sustainable production. The objective is to increase market share in the woodworking sector by commercializing better performing solutions.

SPACE HELLAS

The core business of SPH is ICT integration and provision of turn-key IT, telecom and security solutions. SPH plan for exploiting the project's result is twofold. First, the company plans to exploit components of the OASEES solution (in cooperation with the respective partners-IPR owners) to enhance its commercial IoT offerings, mostly in the Smart City and Energy management domains. Second, the know-how gained from developing the OASEES SDK, as well as the techniques developed, particularly focusing on DevOps processes, will be used to support and enhance the company's software development and integration activities.

ORGANISMOS TILEPIKOINONION ELLADOS(OTE)

The Hellenic Telecommunications Organization S.A. (OTE) member of the Deutsche Telekom (DT) Group of Companies is the leading telecommunications provider (network and services) in Greece. OTE, together with its subsidiaries, forms one of the leading telecom groups in the southeastern Europe.

OTE will explore and evaluate the developments in IoT-cloud-edge continuum, data exchange, interoperability and sustainability solutions offered by the OASEES project and investigate the potential to transform these advancements into commercial implementation by creating new services using both public and private mobile networks, in collaboration with small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

OTE aims to leverage its extensive expertise in telecommunications and ICT to provide customized IoT applications including those addressed by the OASEES project, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) equipment, access network equipment and business-level services in various vertical industries who will invest in 5G for their digital transformation.

AXON LOGIC

Axon Logic and SENSO are collaborating closely on the development of classical and hybrid quantum convolutional networks for regression prediction for the USE CASE 4. Additionally, both parties are considering the development of hybrid quantum algorithms for classification. Their focus is on assessing the practicality and feasibility of these hybrid quantum solutions, with the goal of publishing their findings.

CAPGEMINI

As the leader of Use Case 6: Smart Swarm Energy harvesting and Predictive Maintenance Wind Turbines within OASEES consortium, we follow to optimize energy consumption and make solutions smarter, supporting the energy transition in its different components, change the way we innovate products and protect the planet by taking into account the complexity of parameters, autonomous systems, under an everything-as-a-service & systems of systems approach and, intelligently apply data science and machine learning technologies to scale industry-specific problems.

CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable presented an overview of the OASEES exploitation strategy. In the beginning of the document the presentation of the current list of identified KERs was outlined. Each KER was accompanied by a description, an IPR analysis, background and foreground assets, and competitor analysis. A SWOT analysis was displayed for each KER evaluating the strengths. Both BMC and VPC were presented as business models are required in the identification process. The deliverable concludes with insights, substantial for a thorough analysis of the key exploitable results and assets.

	of spatial damage distribution																
6	Drone Fleet route optimization				CF												
7	Dynamic Maintenance Plan & LCOE												BF				
8	Energy consumption and production forecasting							B									
9	EVs fleet coordinated recharging to support optimal operation of electricity grid							BCF	BCF								
10	Gaia-X Onboarding API			BF													
11	Multi-location post-earthquake detection system									BF							
12	Multi-Modal Anomaly-Detection Model for Smart Edge Security										BF						
13	Multi-Modal AI-based Vulnerability Detection										BF						
14	NightWatch Edge									BF							
15	Non-intrusive detection of wind turbine blade faults through collaborative swarm collaboration using acoustic data from the blades												BF				

28	Quantum Debugging Framework				BFC													
29	Quantum DevOps		BFC		BFC													
30	Reeducation plan			F														BF
31	Resource allocation algorithms in support of accelerators																	
32	Robotic Swarm powered Smart Factory for I4.0					BFC						BFC						
33	Scientific publications	F	CF													F		
34	Smart Edge-Connected Node for the Analysis of Voice, Articulation and Fluency disorders in Parkinson Disease				BF													BF
35	Smart Swarm Energy harvesting and Predictive Maintenance Wind turbines												BF					
36	SSI for IoT and edge devices		BF			BFC												
37	Sum Secrecy Rate Optimization for Rotary-Wing UAV Communications System with Quantum Actor-Critic Reinforcement Learning																	FC
38	Support for imec HW accelerated vision/radar in UC3		BFC															C
39	System and procedure for detecting irregularities in wind turbine blades												BF					

